

MAELSTROM

MArinE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D2.4

Impact assessment report in the two demo sites (Lagoon of Venice and the Porto region)

14/02/2025

MAELSTROM

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Executive Summary

The MAELSTROM project aims to test and evaluate innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in different coastal environments, also assessing their impact on the ecosystems in chosen demo sites and evaluating the economic and societal benefits of the MAELSTROM solutions within local economies. The purpose of the Deliverable 2.4 is to provide the results of the surveys of the ecological status of demo sites (Venice coastal area and Porto region) before and after the testing of the cleaning technologies. For the two demo sites, the Deliverable describes: 1) the methodologies for the monitoring of marine litter and microplastics and the methods used for the evaluation of the state of the biological communities characterising of the Demo sites, including the Passive Acoustic Monitoring; 2) the results of the pre-cleaning environmental assessment in the Porto region, as the Bubble Barrier has been deployed in November 2023; 3) the results of the post-cleaning environmental assessment performed in both Demo sites.

In the Venice coastal area, the results highlighted a general decrease in microplastic presence in sediments and biota over time. The fish community showed an increase in the number of fish species at both sites and a marked increase in the number of individuals at the coastal site in autumn 2023 with respect to the pre-cleaning surveys. The monitoring of macro litter in the cleaned area showed a decrease of macro-litter items on the seafloor. In the Canal Grande, where no cleanings were performed, the amount of the litter increased by 200% between 2013 and 2023.

The environmental assessment in the Ave River estuary shows that its status can be classified as moderate to poor with respect to nutrients and the biological element benthic macroinvertebrates, respectively. Moreover, the floating macro-litter showed a significant reduction in quantities after passing through the Bubble Barrier.

Although the removal technologies were successfully demonstrated in both sites, representing an effective remediation strategy, the environmental monitoring results highlight the need of preventive measures to reduce plastic pollution in both Demo sites.

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1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex question to the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy. MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions providing also a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) enhances social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

2 MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of:

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3 Aim of the Deliverable

Deliverable 2.4 reports and describes the methods used and the results obtained in the Task 2.5 Cleaning impact assessment in the Venice coastal area (IT), and in the Task 2.6 Cleaning impact assessment in the Porto region (PT). This report includes the results of the assessment of marine litter (ML) presence and the state of the biological communities after the cleaning operations performed with the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in the Venice coastal areas (i.e. the coastal and lagoon sites) and before and after the implementation of the Bubble Barrier in the Demo site of the Porto region (the Ave estuary).

As for the Venice coastal area, the results included in this Deliverable refer to: a) 4 surveys carried out after the cleaning operations in the lagoon site of Sacca Fisola, and b) 1 additional survey before the cleaning operations and 3 surveys after the cleaning operations in the abandoned mussel farm. The methods and results here reported are related to the monitoring and the quantification of seafloor macro-litter, the evaluation of microplastics analysed in surface water, sediments and biota (bivalves and fish) and the monitoring of macro-zoobenthic and fish communities. Moreover, the presence of microplastics having sizes $> 20 \mu\text{m}$ in the surface waters and the biological communities colonizing the collected macro-litter (fouling communities) were also analysed. Lastly, a non-intrusive monitoring method based on passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) was tested to assess the presence of vocalizing fish species in the abandoned mussel farm. The data acquired with the traditional fish species monitoring and with PAM were compared.

In the Ave estuary (Porto region), the Bubble Barrier was installed in November 2023, consequently the results here reported refer both to pre-cleaning surveys and post-cleaning surveys (from November 2023 on). Floating macroplastics were quantified through visual monitoring during the ecosystem state assessment, whereas microplastic particles were evaluated in the water surface. Water quality and the ecosystem ecological status were determined through the metrics defined by the Water Framework Directive for transitional waters. General physical and chemical parameters, analysis of biological parameters and hydro-morphological elements were also characterized. The methodologies followed the same protocols described on Deliverable 2.3 to assure that the results are comparable.

4 State-of-the art of the Demo sites

In this section, we intend to give a brief description of the Italian and Portuguese Demo sites, and an overview of the previous information available on the sources of marine litter and microplastics in the two geographical areas.

4.1 The Italian demo site: Venice coastal area

The Gulf of Venice is the northern part of the Adriatic Sea, extending eastward for 95 km from the Po River delta (Italy), to the coast of Istria (Slovenia and Croatia) (Figure 1). The Gulf is subject to anthropic pressures such as nutrient loads from agriculture, pollution from coastal towns, fishery, coastal and maritime tourism, traffic from maritime routes.

The lagoon of Venice is located in the northwest part of the Gulf (45° 12' N) and is the largest Mediterranean lagoon (surface 500 km², vertical north-south length 50 km, mean horizontal width 15 km). Three inlets connect the lagoon with the open sea (Lido, Malamocco and Chioggia, from north to south). The bathymetry is characterised by the presence of navigable channels, tidal flats and shoals. Its average depth is approximately 1 m, with only 5% deeper than 5 m (some navigable channels are deeper than 15 m) and 75 % is shallower than 2 m. The lagoon of Venice is characterised by various point and non-point sources of pollutant inputs. These sources are often localized in specific areas, mainly deriving from the industries of the Porto Marghera district, the sewage and urban runoff from the cities of Venice and Chioggia, and the run-off from the drainage basins which are intensively urbanized and cultivated.

The entire Venice coastal area is impacted by marine litter in several ways (Pasquini et al., 2016; Liubartseva et al., 2016, Liubartseva et al., 2018). In particular, accumulation of marine litter on the bottom has been showed to be relevant (the western gulf of Venice was shown to be one of the most impacted area in the Adriatic Sea by Fortibuoni et al., 2019). Fisheries and aquaculture have been demonstrated to contribute to ML pollution (Deliverable D2.1). This is confirmed also by the larger coastal area of the Northern Adriatic Sea (e.g. (Fortibuoni et al., 2019; Vlachogianni et al., 2018; Pasquini et al., 2016; Strafella et al., 2015).

The Port of Venice is Italy's eighth largest port in traffic volume terms, and one of the most important in the Mediterranean for cruise ships, catering to an enormous flow of people and vehicles. Maritime traffic has been already recognized as a source for

marine litter in the area (Liubartseva et al., 2018). The Port of Chioggia, located at the southern edge of the Venice lagoon, ranks as second among the Italian fishing ports. The fishing fleet from Chioggia is among the most numerous and best equipped of the Northern Adriatic.

Figure 1– The Gulf of Venice in the North Adriatic Sea and the Lagoon of Venice.

4.2 The Portuguese demo site: Porto region

Located in the northwest of Portugal, the Ave River hydrological basin (Figure 2) has an approximate area of 1390 km². From its source in Serra da Cabreira to its mouth in Vila do Conde the river length is 101 km (Rocha et al., 2019). The Ave estuarine area belongs to the Vila do Conde municipality, in the district of Porto.

The Ave River differs from other northern Portuguese rivers not only because of its high pollution levels, but also because of the large spatial and temporal variability of pollutant concentration (Gonçalves and Alpuim, 2011; Rocha et al., 2019). Overall, the watercourses of the Ave hydrographic basin (Figure 2) present serious disturbances, regarding physical, chemical and biological levels, with few exceptions recorded only in the upstream area close to the springs. These disturbances have several effects in the ecosystem, namely the degradation of the riparian curtain, the alteration of the channel, and the poor quality of the water. As expected, these disturbances have significant consequences on the aquatic communities. The surrounding area of the Ave estuary is mainly urban, except on the left margin where a small wasteland with a few species of ruderal plants and very low fauna densities can be found (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Maps of a) the location of the hydrographic basin of the Ave River in Portugal, b) the Ave hydrographic basin land use characterization, and c) the Ave estuary with land use characterization in the surrounding area of the study sites.

Along the hydrographic basin of Ave River, several pressures were identified contributing to the occurrence of litter in the aquatic ecosystem (Figure 2b). This area is one of the most industrialized areas of Portugal, hosting a huge number of industries, such as those of textiles and surface treatment (Figure 2b), metal plating, leather tanning, rubber and plastic, cutlery and metalworking manufactures (Rocha et al., 2019). These lead to high levels of pollution and to a decrease of water quality that have been registered in this region during the last decades (Couto et al., 2019). Other activities also contribute to the impact of marine litter in the aquatic ecosystem, such as landfills, aquaculture plants, port facilities, and tourism. The latter more pronounced in the Ave River estuary due to the urban activities of the fishing town of Vila do Conde, located in the northern margin of the estuarine area.

5 Case study: Venice coastal area, Italy

5.1 Ecological assessment in the Venice demo sites

The demo site of the Venice coastal area includes two different areas, one inside the lagoon (1. Lagoon site) and one at sea (2. Coastal site) (Figure 3). Both areas are characterised by historically accumulated marine litter. The identification of the demonstration sites in Venice was based on field surveys, on previous data and information available on ML presence and abundances for the Venice coastal area (see D2.3 for more details). The MAELSTROM DoA foresees that specific monitoring activities had to take place in proximity of a mussel farm to assess the state of macro zoo-benthic and fish communities, before and after the technology removal operations. Consequently, we decided that the Coastal Demo Site should be near a mussel farm concession at sea (where most of the mussel farms are located), whereas the Lagoon Site should be characterised by the presence of urban-derived litter.

Figure 3 – Venice coastal area demo sites

Regarding the Lagoon site, in the framework of the MarGnet Project (Mapping and recycling of marine litter and ghost nets on the sea-floor,

EASME/EMFF/2017/1.2.1.12/S2/05/SI2.789314), the area of Sacca Fisola was monitored in the 2019 and a ML hotspot was found. The surveyed area was characterised by the presence of various items such as tires, poles, crates, boats and other items (Madricardo et al., 2020). This area was selected for the MAELSTROM Project.

Sacca Fisola Island is located along the Giudecca Canal, southeast of the historical centre of Venice (Figure 4). It is an artificial island, created in the 1960s. From 1969 to 1984 Sacca San Biagio, another small artificial island connected to Sacca Fisola, housed an incinerator for municipal solid waste. The area still hosts the Veritas (the Venice waste management company) worksite, where waste is delivered daily.

The sampling area is located in a minor navigation channel (few meters deep), mainly used by boats for transportation of goods and by residents and also by the vessels of the Venetian Waste Management Authority (Veritas) to deliver waste.

Figure 4 – Venice Lagoon demo site 2: Lagoon site - Sacca Fisola. Bathymetry and marine litter items detected in 2019 in the framework of the MarGnet Project.

As for the Coastal Site, an abandoned concession for mussel harvesting was chosen. Non-operational concessions have some advantages with respect to active ones for testing innovative technologies: the environment and the sea bottom are characterised by the presence of all the waste deriving from mussel farm activities, but here testing operations can be carried out without interfering with the economic

activities of farming. This is also important considering the size of the platform. The attention was focused on an abandoned mussel farm located in front of the Sile river mouth at about 1.7 nautical miles from the coast and having a total surface of 1.960.000 m² (Figure 5). The area has a mean depth of about 14 m. The mussel farm was disused some years ago, but the owner left at sea all the structures used to harvest mussels. In agreement with the MAELSTROM team that implemented the technology and with the Coast Guard, it was decided that the Seabed Cleaning Platform would operate in an area of about 2% of the total area of the mussel farm, corresponding to a surface of about 40.000 m².

Figure 5 - Venice Lagoon demo site 1: coastal site – abandoned mussel farm.

An integrated framework was defined to assess the status of marine ecosystems in both the demo sites of the Venice coastal area, including the state of contamination from macro- and micro-litter. The framework is illustrated in Figure 6. Seafloor mapping was used to assess macro-litter presence on the seafloor. Waters and sediments were also characterised for the presence of microplastics. Community state and content of microplastics were assessed for some biological compartments, namely macrozoobenthos and fish.

Figure 6 – Scheme summarizing the timeframe of the monitoring surveys and of the cleaning operations (A) and the integrated assessment framework defined to study the Venice demo site (B).

5.1.1 Mapping of the study areas

Underwater acoustic remote sensing was carried out to assess the presence of macrolitter on the seafloor and the removal technology effectiveness. Mapping activities were performed after cleaning operations to provide estimates of seafloor cleaning capacity. With this aim, high resolution multibeam echosounders (MBES) were used to map the area of Sacca Fisola and the abandoned mussel farm in the Venice coastal area. Thanks to the cameras of the robotic platform, it was possible to collect and analyse accurately georeferenced videos to ground truth the interpretation of the targets identified though the multibeam data.

Moreover, a further survey was carried out in the highly traffic impacted Canal Grande in the heart of Venice to monitor the presence of litter on its seafloor. Madricardo et al (2019) shown that the Canal Grande was a marine litter hotspot within the lagoon (see Figure 7 for an overview of the mapped area location).

Figure 7 - Areas mapped with the MBES in the Venice coastal area: Sacca Fisola, the abandoned mussel farm, demo sites for the Seabed Cleaning Platform and the Grand Canal in the Venice city center.

The same instrumental set up used during the multibeam surveys carried out before the cleaning operations (see D2.3) were used in three other surveys at Sacca Fisola in November 2022, and May and December 2023, in two other surveys at the abandoned mussel farm in May and December 2023 and in April 2023 in the Canal Grande. The surveys were performed with a Kongsberg EM-2040c compact single head multi-frequency multibeam system, 400 beams per swath, 1° beamwidth at 400 KHz. The operational frequency was set to 320 KHz. In May 2022, a Kongsberg EM-2040p single head multi-frequency multibeam system was used, still ensuring the same technical characteristics.

The MBES was pole-mounted on the CNR research vessel Litus, a 11-m-long boat with 1.5-m-deep draft. The positioning system was a Seapath 380 system, supplied by Real Time Kinematic (RTK) online correction and integrated with the Kongsberg motion sensor MRU 5 and with a Dual Antenna GPS, that allow to take in account for ship positioning and for pitch, roll, heave and yaw movements, Figure 8.

The system was completed by a Valeport mini SVS sensor, attached close to the transducer to continuously measure the sound velocity for the beamforming. Sound velocity profiles (SVPs) were collected with a Valeport SWiFT SVP sound velocity profiler every day at the beginning of the activities or whenever the temperature and salinity of the water changed significantly, as the tidal phases changed. Data was logged, displayed and checked in real-time by the Kongsberg data acquisition and control software SIS (Seafloor Information System).

Water column backscatter intensity data were collected as well to identify the presence of suspended items in the water column.

The processing of the acquired data was carried out using the Caris HIPS & SIPS 11 software following the standard procedures for data conversion, tide correction (tide data provided by ISPRA, referred to the local tidal reference *Zero Mareografico di Punta della Salute* ZMPS 1897), creation of surfaces, cleaning of spurious data and application of refraction coefficients for the correction of speed of sound errors.

The bathymetric data processed in Caris HIPS & SIPS were imported into ARCGIS for further analysis.

Figure 8 - Litus Vessel and MBES system.

At Sacca Fisola, 80 navigation lines were necessary to produce bathymetric maps. The extension of the covered area varies between 0.05 Km² and 0.08 Km². Bathymetry ranges between 1 to 5.7 meters (Figure 9 and Figure 10).

Figure 9 - Surveyed lines of Sacca Fisola: (a) May 2022 survey (b) November 2022 survey (c) May 2023 survey (d) December 2023 survey.

Figure 10 - Bathymetry of Sacca Fisola: (a) May.2022 survey (b) November 2022 survey (c) May.2023 survey (d) December 2023 survey.

At the abandoned mussel farm, a pre-cleaning survey was repeated on 28th May 2023, just before the cleaning operations. The first pre-cleaning survey was carried out in spring 2022, but it was not possible to operate the Seabed Cleaning Platform in 2022 due to adverse weather conditions. This extra-survey allowed a more accurate and updated estimate of the presence of litter. The second survey, after the cleaning operations, was carried out on the 12th of December 2023, covering the whole Abandoned Mussel Farm area. A total of 23 lines was navigated (Figure 11) to produce the two bathymetric maps in Figure 12, covering respectively 0.04 Km² and 0.36 Km² for May and December 2023.

Figure 11 - Survey lines at the abandoned mussel farm: (a) May.2023 survey (b) December 2023 survey.

Figure 12 - Bathymetry of the area of the abandoned mussel farm: (a) May.2023 survey (b) December 2023 survey.

At the Canal Grande, data were recorded from 14th to 15th April 2023: the area, about 0.03 Km² (Figure 13) was covered by 35 navigation lines and had a depth ranging from 1 to 5.6 m (Figure 14).

Figure 13 - Surveyed lines in Canal Grande of the April 2023 survey.

Figure 14 - Bathymetry of Canal Grande collected in April 2023.

5.1.2 Assessment of the biological community

5.1.2.1 *Macro-zoobenthos assessment*

Soft bottom macrozoobenthic communities were characterized both in the Coastal and Lagoon sites. Moreover, the fouling community was characterized on a subsample of marine litter items collected during the removal operations.

Soft bottom macrobenthos

In both the Coastal and Lagoon sites, sampling stations interested (impact) or not (control) by cleaning activities were compared, minimizing other environmental sources of variation. The positioning of monitoring sampling stations was originally defined before 2022 pre-cleaning sampling on the basis of relevant environmental information for the study scale (mainly bathymetric and backscatter data collected by preliminary MBES surveys carried out respectively on February 2022 in the area of the coastal site and October 2021 in the area of the lagoon site), as well as the planned location of cleaning activities. In the lagoon site, three stations were defined: LV1 (on the planned cleaning area), LV2 (control) and LV3 (additional, in case more information would have been required, with only 2022 sample having been analysed) (see Figure 15 and Table 1).

Figure 15 – Map of sampling stations in the Lagoon site.

Table 1 – Geographic coordinates (WGS84) of sampling stations.

Station	Description	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (m)
LV1	cleaning area	45°25.506' N	12°18.619' E	4.5
LV2	control	45°25.491' N	12°18.794' E	4.6
LV3	additional	45°25.563' N	12°18.451' E	5.1

In the coastal site, three stations were initially defined: CS1 (on the planned cleaning area), CS2 (control) and CS3, the last one as additional in case more information would have been required. Since cleaning operations were instead performed on another location nearby, a new monitoring station C4 was sampled since September 2023 campaign, discontinuing the analysis of CS1 samples (see Figure 16 and Table 2).

Samplings were performed twice per year in 2023 and 2024. At the Lagoon site of Sacca Fisola samplings were carried out on 04/04/2023, 27/09/2023, 12/03/2024 and 06/09/2024, after the cleaning operations performed in September 2022. In the abandoned mussel farm samplings were carried out on 18/04/2023, 29/09/2023, 03/04/2024 and 16/09/2024, the first one before the cleaning operations (May 2023). All the samplings were carried out on board the vessel M/B Litus (CNR-ISMAR), apart from 18/04/2023 sampling, which was performed on board M/B Aretusa (CNR-ISMAR).

Figure 16 – Map of sampling stations in the abandoned mussel farm, Coastal site; the “Experimental field” is also showed.

Table 2 – Geographic coordinates (WGS84) of sampling stations.

Station	Description	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (m)
CS1	planned cleaning area (discontinued in September 2023)	45°27.056' N	12°35.631' E	14.8
CS2	control	45°27.126' N	12°35.582' E	14.6
CS3	additional	45°27.046' N	12°35.678' E	14.9
CS4	cleaning area (since September 2023)	45°27.176' N	12°35.517' E	14.4

The same protocol was applied on both marine and lagoon soft bottom macrobenthos. The protocol includes sampling by grabs (three replicates for each station), taxonomic determination and quantitative analysis of the community matrix. The sampling procedure overall follows the approach established by the Marine Strategy Framework Directive protocols implemented in Italy (MATTM, 2018). Quantitative benthic samples were collected with a Van Veen grab having a surface area of 0.1 m² and a volume of approximately 17 l (Figure 17). Sampled sediment volume was required to be greater than 50% or 75% of the grab capacity, respectively

for sandy and muddy sediments. The collected sediment was transferred to numbered buckets. Field information was recorded on data sheets. In laboratory, samples were immediately sieved at 1 mm mesh size, gently washing them with filtered sea water. The retained material, including macrobenthic organisms, shell detritus and other residual material, was stored in 70% ethanol.

Figure 17– The Van Veen grab used for sampling activities.

The analysis of the samples followed consolidated procedures (Gambi & Dappiano, 2003). Samples were treated with rose bengal dye and sorted by means of a binocular stereoscope (6.4x - 40x). All macrozoobenthos taxa were separated from the matrix and divided into homogeneous taxonomic groups (phylum or class) and kept in a 70% ethanol solution. All the specimens were identified using main taxonomic keys available for the different groups and counted. The determination was carried out at the species level or at the highest possible resolution, in that case open nomenclature rules were applied (Sigovini et al., 2016). The World Register of Marine Species (<https://www.marinespecies.org>, updated on 31/01/2025) was used as taxonomic reference.

Data were organized as abundance matrix. Community structure was described by main univariate ecological descriptors, composition in terms of main taxonomic groups (at the phylum or class level). Selected univariate descriptors include abundance, richness, diversity, biotic and multimetric indices, as listed hereafter:

- density, Nm⁻²
- species richness, S
- Shannon index, $H' = -\sum p_i \log_2 p_i$ ($p_i = n_i/N$, with n_i being the i -th taxon abundance; Shannon & Weaver, 1949). It expresses the "uncertainty" in predicting which species a randomly selected individual belongs to, with values ranging between 0 and ∞ . Like the other diversity indices, it takes into account the richness and distribution of abundances among taxa. A high sample size is assumed ($N \rightarrow \infty$).
- AMBI biotic index (Borja et al., 2000). Biotic indices are based on the paradigm that the taxonomic composition is affected by the quality of the system, in terms of the quantitative ratio (abundances) between sensitive and tolerant species, following the theoretical models by Pearson & Rosenberg (1978), Glémarec & Hily (1981) and other previous authors focusing on the organic enrichment of the sediments (see also Tagliapietra et al., 2012). However, biotic indices have been also applied to other types of impacts. Calculation steps are the following: 1) taxa are attributed to one of five "ecological groups" describing the taxon sensitivity, based on lists of species (December 2020 version, <https://ambi.azti.es/>; if the taxon is missing, a class has been assigned when possible based on expert opinion); 2) a biotic coefficient ranging between 1 and 6 is calculated according to the formula: $BC = (0 \times \%GI) + (1.5 \times \%GII) + (3 \times \%GIII) + (4.5 \times \%GIV) + (6 \times \%GV)$ (GI-GV are the percentage abundances of the five ecological groups; 7 is given in case of azoic samples); 3) a discrete biotic index BI 1-7 may be attributed according to reference BC intervals, however it has not been applied in the present analysis.
- M-AMBI multimetric index (Bald et al., 2005; Muxika et al., 2007). The index integrates S, H' and BC through complex multivariate calculations, however it has been demonstrated that it approximates the simple mean of normalised metrics (Sigovini et al. 2013), with 0-1 normalisation calculated over the following range: a minimum value corresponding to lowest theoretical conditions ($S = 0$, $H' = 0$, $BC = 6$) and a maximum value corresponding either to given high-quality reference conditions (which generally differ according to the monitored environment) or to the highest values in the dataset (the lowest value in the case of BC), the latter being applied in the present analysis (separately for marine and lagoon community data). The M-AMBI index therefore assumes values between 0 and 1 (or slightly higher than 1).

Of all the indices, only AMBI is independent of the sampled surface, since it does not include richness in the calculation. Therefore, it is not possible a direct comparison

of the results with studies where a different surface of sediment has been sampled. Indices were calculated on replicates, and then mean and standard deviation were calculated for each sample.

Litter fouling

During the marine litter cleaning activities on both the coastal and lagoon site, fouling has been sampled on a subset of collected litter items. From each item, samples were performed by scraping off an area of 0.1 m² from the part exposed to colonization by epifauna. For the lagoon site, 5 items (4 tires and a metal frame) were subject to scraping on 26-27/09/2022. For the coastal site, only 3 samples of sufficient quality could be acquired during May-June 2023 cleaning operations, 2 plastic buoys retained near the seabed and a section of synthetic rope, all of them leftover aquaculture equipment. In laboratory, samples were sieved at 1 mm mesh size, gently washing them with filtered sea water, and the retained material stored in 70% ethanol. The analyses followed the same protocol for soft bottom macrozoobenthos.

5.1.2.2 Monitoring of the fish community through sampling campaigns

Fish fauna sampling activities were carried out both at the lagoon site (Sacca Fisola) and at the coastal site (abandoned mussel farm) semi-annually for two years (Figure 18), according to the calendar shown in Table 3. Considering that the cleaning operations were carried out by the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in September 2022 at Sacca Fisola and in June 2023 at the abandoned mussel farm, the fish fauna assessment was carried out through the organization of different number of monitoring campaigns at the two sites. In particular, for the lagoon site, four post cleaning monitoring campaigns were carried out in: April 2023, November 2023, April 2024 and November 2024; whereas for the coastal site, one additional pre-cleaning monitoring campaign was carried in March 2023, followed by three post cleaning campaigns (in December 2023 and in April and September 2024).

Figure 18 - (A) Satellite image showing the sampling stations in the coastal site, (B) Details of the sampling area.

Table 3 - Calendar of Fish fauna campaigns

Coastal site		Lagoon site	
29-30 March 2023	2° pre-cleaning	1-5 April 2023	1° post-cleaning
5-6 December 2023	1° post-cleaning	2-6 November 2023	2° post-cleaning
4-5 April 2024	2° post-cleaning	8-16 April 2024	3° post-cleaning
22-23 September 2024	3° post-cleaning	27-28 November 2024	4° post-cleaning

The use of fishing nets was preferred to visual census sampling methodology to optimise the sampling effort and to adopt the most effective sampling tool allowing to obtain comparable results overcoming the potential issue related to the high turbidity that often characterises both areas. It is well known that turbidity is a parameter that could affect the results of the visual census methodology. On the other hand, the use of fishing nets is a widely used method to monitor fish community in these environments (CVN, study B.6.85 and B.6.85/II, Fiorin et al., 2008; Riccato et al., 2008).

In the coastal site (i.e. the abandoned mussel farm) different types of nets were employed in order to sample a wide range of ecological and size fish guilds. In particular, four sets of similar nets, each one consisting of a small trap and three 50 meters long nets (33 mm trammel net; 40 mm gillnet; 50 mm gillnet) were displaced for 1 day in 4 different stations within the sampling area Figure 18 and Table 4). Given the presence on the bottom of numerous objects (such as the mooring blocks used to anchor the structures of the mussel farm), the nets were placed in neighbouring areas with few or no obstacles in order to preserve the integrity of the nets and to conduct

the sampling successfully. The reduced distance from the sampling area was considered suitable to provide a reliable picture of both benthic and pelagic fish species characterising the area. Sampling activities were carried out in collaboration with professional fishers

Table 4 - Coordinates of fish fauna sampling stations in the coastal site

Sampling stations	Latitude	Longitude
S1	45°27.106'	12°35.544'
S2	45°27.012'	12°35.475'
S3	45°26.991'	12°35.661'
S4	45°27.085'	12°35.725'

Figure 19 - Fish sampling activities in the coastal site.

Fish were identified according to their species. Moreover, the main morphometric parameters (length and weight) of each individual were recorded. Abundance and biomass data were then standardised in terms of catch per unit effort (CPUE), i.e. number of individuals captured by 150 m net in one fishing day and grams of fish captured by 150 m net in one fishing day, respectively. Mean values (and standard deviations) of CPUE per species were then calculated.

Fish sampling in the lagoon site was performed using particular fishing gear (fyke nets), locally used in the lagoon, positioned on the seabed of the shallow waters

(maximum depth 1.8 meters) for a period ranging from 1 to 10 days. Each fishing gear consists of a 130-140-cm-high net barrier (“tressa”), having a minimum mesh size of 14 mm and a variable length, connected to a series of fyke nets (“bertovelli”). The gear was fixed to the seabed with poles. Ten fyke nets were placed within the sampling site close to the area where removal activities took place (Figure 20 and Table 5).

Figure 20 – (A) Satellite image showing the removal activity area in the lagoon site, (B) Details of the fish fauna sampling area.

Table 5 – Coordinates of fish fauna sampling area in the lagoon site.

Vertices coordinates	Latitude	Longitude
S1	45° 25,46748'	12° 18.59928'
S2	45° 25,48974'	12° 18.6144'
S3	45° 25,53156'	12° 18.47724'
S4	45° 25.50822'	12° 18.46206'

Sampling activities were carried out in collaboration with professional fishers (Figure 21). Fish were divided according to their species and the weight was recorded for each individual. Abundance and biomass data were then standardised in terms of catch per unit effort (CPUE), i.e. number of individuals captured by fyke net in one fishing day and grams of fish captured by fyke net in one fishing day, respectively. Mean values (and standard deviations) of CPUE per species were then calculated.

Figure 21 - Fish sampling activities in the lagoon site

If organisms belonging to species listed under protection at international, European and national level according to CITES, IUCN, Habitat Directive (92/43/EEC), Natura 2000 Network were found in the nets, they were promptly released back into the environment after biometric data had been recorded.

The data collected in both coastal and lagoon sites (number of individuals, species) were used to calculate three biodiversity indexes: species richness, Margalef index and Shannon index.

5.1.2.3 *Monitoring of the fish community through Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM)*

Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) has emerged as a powerful, non-invasive tool for studying marine environments (Picciulin et al., 2020). PAM involves the use of underwater hydrophones to detect and record sounds produced by marine organisms (biophony), environmental processes (geophony), and anthropogenic activities (anthrophony) (Ross et al., 2023). This method enables scientists to track vocalizing species, assess biodiversity, study animal behavior, and monitor human impacts such as shipping noise and industrial operations. By continuously capturing underwater soundscapes, PAM provides valuable long-term data that enhances our understanding of marine ecosystems (Carriço et al., 2020). Its applications range from detecting whale migrations and monitoring fish populations to assessing ecosystem health and enforcing conservation policies. As technological advances improve data collection and analysis, PAM is becoming an increasingly essential tool for marine research and conservation efforts.

In the framework of the MAELSTROM project, passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) was conducted using a hydrophone deployed before and after the cleaning campaign

carried out at the abandoned mussel farm. The primary aim of this acoustic monitoring was to analyze underwater soundscapes to detect the presence of soniferous organisms, with particular attention to fish and potentially invertebrate components. The same area was previously analyzed for its biophonical and anthrophonical sources by Picciulin et al. (2016) and Colla et al. (2018). Recording activities took place during summer evenings (18:30–23:00 h) at six stations along a transect parallel to the coastline, both inside and outside the mussel farm. The results from Colla et al. (2018) indicate that *Sciaena umbra* actively selects the internal structures of the mussel farm as a spawning habitat while avoiding the sandy areas outside.

Continuous PAM surveys were conducted during the summers of 2022 and 2024 (from August 11 to September 28, 2022, and from August 13 to August 26, 2024) for a total of 1148 hours in 2022 and 320 hours for 2024.

Recordings were obtained by using an autonomous passive underwater acoustic recorder, the Sono-Vault hydrophone by Develogic Subsea Systems, which is capable of sampling in both 16-bit and 24-bit modes. The recorder is featured with an omnidirectional broadband Neptune Sonar D60 Hydrophone characterized by a sensitivity around -192.7 dB re $1\text{V}/\mu\text{Pa}$ (flat frequency response: $10\text{ Hz} - 20\text{ kHz} \pm 3\text{ dB}$). For this survey, the hydrophone was configured with a sampling rate of 48 kHz , 16 bit and a gain of 3 dB , generating 1-hour WAV files. The hydrophone was deployed at a depth of 14 m ($45^{\circ}27'1.52''\text{N} / 12^{\circ}35'34.69''\text{E}$) with a mooring system consisting of a weight ballast, the logger itself secured by polypropylene rope and extra flotation, as illustrated in Figure 22.

Figure 22 - Mooring system and acoustic recorder.

To ensure clear visualization of low-frequency components of the soundscape, the recordings were resampled at a frequency of 6000 Hz using the software Audacity and then visualized and analyzed manually using Raven Pro 1.6 software by aural and visual assessment of the spectrograms (Hanning window, FFT 512.). Each 1-hour WAV file was filtered with a lower limit of 50 Hz to eliminate noise from electrical components and an upper limit of 3000 Hz, as fish vocalizations typically fall within this frequency range (Picciulin et al., 2020). The presence of biological sounds was noted.

The data obtained with the Passive Acoustic Monitoring were then compared to those obtained with traditional methods for the monitoring of the fish community.

5.1.3 Microplastic assessment

Concentrations of microplastic particles were determined in different environmental matrices, both abiotic and biotic, at Sacca Fisola and at the abandoned mussel farm. In particular, their abundance was determined in surface waters, sediments and biota. As for the quantification of microplastic particles in the biota, the mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* or the oysters *Magallana gigas* and *Ostreola stentina* were chosen due to their filter feeding behaviour and because these species, due to the high tolerance to a wide range of environmental parameters, are widespread in marine as well as in the lagoon environment. Different species of fish were used to analyse the microplastic in their visceral tract, according to their presence and abundance in the coastal area and in the lagoon site.

Strict measures were taken during sampling, sample preparation and analysis to minimise the risk of environmental contamination. Before each analysis, the work area was thoroughly cleaned and glassware was washed with a specific detergent, if necessary, and then rinsed with 31 µm filtered water.

The number of operators present in the laboratory was limited and the colour of clothing worn under the lab coat was recorded. Procedural controls were carried out in parallel with sample processing; daily checks were performed to assess environmental contamination: glass microfibre filters were placed in the work area and analysed at the end of the day using a stereomicroscope (Leica Stereozoom S9D) to monitor airborne particles.

The extracted microplastics were analysed under a stereomicroscope, counted and classified according to shape (spheres, pellets, flat or irregular fragments, sheets and

fibres or filaments) and colour (white, black, red, blue, green, transparent or another colour) (Vital et al., 2021).

5.1.3.1 *Microplastics assessment in surface waters (size range from 5 mm to 330 μm)*

Floating microplastics were collected using a Manta trawl with a 330- μm mesh net and a 0.6 \times 0.3-m rectangular net opening (Figure 23). In each sampling site 3 replicates were performed. Samplings were always carried out in calm conditions, with wind speed not exceeding 2 on the Beaufort wind force scale, since with stronger winds, the rough conditions prevent reliable sample collection on the sea surface. During sampling, the Manta trawl was lowered from the vessel taking care to position it outside the boat's wake and was maintained in flotation for 20 min with a boat speed of 1-3 knots. The Manta trawl was provided with a flowmeter to calculate the volume of water passing through the net. After each sampling, the Manta net was thoroughly washed to collect all the debris particles stuck to the mesh and samples were transferred into 1-L glass jars. During sample transport and processing, precautions were taken to avoid sample contamination: only glass and metal (preferably stainless steel) tools, cotton coats, and nitrile gloves were used.

Figure 23 – Manta trawl during sampling operation.

Once in laboratory, samples were thoroughly shaken to facilitate detachment of the microplastics from the walls of the 1-L glass container and then filtered through two metal sieves, 5 mm and 300 μm mesh-size, rinsing the glass container several times with filtered sea water (31 μm). The fraction retained by the 5 mm sieve, mainly consisting of plant debris and planktonic organisms, was thoroughly washed with filtered seawater to remove any adhering microplastics. The obtained fraction, i.e.

floating plastic fragments and the organic materials that precipitated, was then sorted by microscopic inspection. The results were expressed as the number of particles per cubic meters (Vianello et al., 2018).

5.1.3.2 *Microplastics assessment in surface waters (size range from 5 mm to 20 µm)*

As required by the Reviewer after the RP1 review meeting, additional samples of surface water were collected to analyse the microplastic particles lower than 330 µm. In particular, we sampled particles with size ranges from 20 µm to 5 mm.

Water samples were taken from the surface water using 5 litre Niskin bottles. For each site, water collected from four bottles (20 litres in total) was filtered through a metal sieve with a 20µm mesh size. The retained particles were carefully removed and collected using filtered water (20 µm) and stainless-steel tools to minimize contamination from the environment. The collected material was stored in glass containers.

In the laboratory, the organic matter of the samples was digested with 10% hydrogen peroxide for 24 hours. Density separation was then carried out using ipersaline solution with a density of 1.2 g/cm³. 250 ml of filtered salt water was added to each sample and the mixture was thoroughly shaken in a separating funnel. After stirring, the samples decanted for 24 hours.

The resulting supernatant was collected and filtered using a vacuum pump through a 5.0 µm porosity filter placed over a glass microfibre filter. To minimise loss of microplastics, the walls of the separating funnels were thoroughly rinsed with 20 µm filtered water. The collected microplastics were analysed under a stereomicroscope and the results were expressed as MPs per cubic metre of water.

5.1.3.3 *Microplastic assessment in sediments*

Five replicate samples of superficial sediments were collected in each sampling site using a Van Veen grab. The top 5 cm of sediment was collected using a metal spoon and then store in 1-L glass container. Sediments were then rapidly transferred to the laboratory, where the analyses were performed. Microplastics were extracted from each bulk sediment replicate through the density separation according to Frias et al. (2018).

For each replicate sample 250 g (w.w.) of sediment was homogenized using a metal spoon and treated with 100 ml of 10% hydrogen peroxide. The samples were re-homogenized for at least 1 min and then maintained at room temperature for 18-24 hours. The samples were then washed with filtered water and the microplastic particles were extracted from sediments by density separation procedure. Briefly, 750 ml of NaCl filtered hypersaline solution was added to each sample. The samples were stirred for at least one minute and then left to settle for 1 hour. The supernatant containing the microplastic particles was then filtered using a steel sieve with 38 μm mesh size. For each replicate the extraction procedure was repeated three consecutive times to allow a more effective separation of the microplastics. The three extracted fractions were finally resuspended in Milli-Q water and observed at the stereomicroscope.

The results were expressed as the number of particles per Kg of dry weight sediment.

To analyse the possible correlation between microplastic concentration in sediments and their grain size, granulometry was determined in an aliquot of each sediment replicate.

Before proceeding with the particle size analysis, the samples were digested with hydrogen peroxide (10%) for 24 h at 40°C to remove any residual organic matter. Subsequently, the sediments were dried at 60°C and then mechanically disaggregated using a mortar and pestle. They were then dry sieved using a vibrating sieve with sieve stacks of 355, 500, 710 and 1000 μm to separate the coarser fractions. The individual fractions were then weighed to relate them to the total weight of the sample. The finer fraction (<355 μm) was diluted in 100 ml of distilled water and sonicated before being analysed using a laser granulometer (LISST-100X, Sequoia Scientific, Inc.), which discretizes the particle size spectrum into 32 classes ranging from 1.90 μm to 381 μm . The concentration values thus obtained were processed and integrated with the data obtained from the sieves.

The main statistical parameters of the distribution and the relative abundances (%) of the sand, silt and clay fractions based on the classification of Udden (1914) and Wentworth (1922) were obtained using the GRADISTAT software (Blott & Pye, 2001).

5.1.3.4 *Microplastic assessment in the biota*

Bivalves (M. galloprovincialis, M. gigas and O. stentina)

For each sample the length of the shell and the weight of the soft tissues of bivalves were recorded individually

The MP particles in bivalves were assessed in 10-20 individuals per sample in the soft tissue according to the method of Bour et al. (2018), slightly modified. The soft tissues were placed in clean beakers, treated with a 10% KOH solution (1:5, weight: volume) and then placed at 50°C for 48 hours to break down the tissues. To facilitate the digestion process, each sample was cut with scissors. The alkaline digestion stage is essential for extracting MPs from biological samples, removing organic material without destroying plastic polymers.

After digestion, 100 ml of a NaCl hypersaline solution (1.2 g/cm³) was added to separate the MPs from digested tissues. After shaking the mixture thoroughly, it was placed in a 500 ml separator funnel and left to decant for 24 hours. The supernatant was collected and passed through a filter with a porosity of 5.0 µm, placed over a glass microfibre filter and aspirated through a vacuum pump.

Results were expressed as number of particles per gram of soft tissue.

Fish

Microplastics in fish were assessed in approximately 20 individuals per survey. However, this number varies as the total number of specimens depends on what was caught during the surveys. For each sample, the length of the fish and the weight of the gastrointestinal tract were recorded.

The samples were treated using the same methods applied for bivalves, the only difference being the digestion time in the oven (24 hours instead of 48 hours), as the intestinal tissues were completely digested after this time. The ratio of hypersaline solution to sample was adjusted to 1:40 instead of 1:20, as increasing this ratio made it easier to separate the supernatant from the rest of the digested tissues.

Results were expressed as number of particles per gram of soft tissue.

5.2 Results

In the following sections, the data obtained from November 2022 onwards, and not previously included in the Deliverable 2.3, are reported.

The following Table 6 illustrates the subdivision of the sampling campaigns into the two Deliverables.

Table 6 – Sampling campaigns according to the cleaning operations and Deliverable 2.3 and Deliverable 2.4.

		Pre-cleaning	Cleaning operations	Post-cleaning (D2.4)
Sacca Fisola (lagoon site)	<i>Mapping</i>	Autumn 2021 (D2.3) Spring 2022 (D2.3)	Autumn 2022 Spring 2023	Autumn 2022 Spring 2023 Autumn 2023
	<i>Ecosystem assessment</i>	Spring 2022 (D2.3)		Autumn 2022 Spring 2023 Autumn 2023 Spring 2024 Late summer 2024
Abandoned mussel farm (coastal area)	<i>Mapping</i>	Winter 2022 (D2.4) Spring 2023 (D2.4)	Spring 2023	Autumn 2023
	<i>Ecosystem assessment</i>	Spring 2022 (D2.3) Spring 2023 (D2.4)		Autumn 2023 Spring 2024 Late summer 2024

5.2.1 Mapping of the study area

Marine litter was mapped using bathymetric data collected during different monitoring campaigns. For the two demonstration sites in the Venice coastal area, i.e. Sacca Fisola and the abandoned mussel farm, bathymetric data were collected in 2022 and 2023, allowing a comparison before and after cleaning operations. For the Grand Canal site, bathymetric data collected within the MAELSTROM Project in 2023 were compared with data collected in 2013 by Madricardo et al. 2017, allowing changes in litter distribution and density to be analysed over a ten-year time scale.

5.2.1.1 Lagoon site: Sacca Fisola

The four datasets collected in Sacca Fisola (May 2022, November 2022, May 2023, December 2023) were analyzed using the semiautomatic ArcGIS tool described in Deliverable 2.3 and the visual classification by different operators of the seafloor items.

To describe the seafloor macrolitter distribution over time of the full area, we selected the two surveys with the largest overlapping areas, i.e. May 2022 and May 2023. In the survey undertaken close to Sacca Fisola in May 2022 (before the first cleaning campaign), 738 items were identified in the area from the seafloor mapping and

identified as crates, tyres, poles, wrecks and unknown (Figure 24). The results are summarized in Table 7.

Figure 24 – Example of the macrolitter items detected on the seafloor in Sacca Fisola area, in the Venice lagoon in November 2022.

Table 7 - Number and density of items detected in Sacca Fisola in the four surveys.

Year	Month	n° mapped items	Mapped Area (Km ²)	Items/km ²	Mapped Area (m ²)	Items/100m ²
2022	May	739	0.036	20620.48	35838.165	2.06
	November	472	0.036	13171.97	35833.678	1.32
2023	May	547	0.039	13975.32	39140.42	1.40
	December	418	0.034	12226.15	34189.00	1.22

The relative variation in the number items in the Sacca Fisola area between the May 2022 and December 2023 is reported in Table 4 and in Figure 6 is illustrated an example of the distribution and typology of items for the November 2022 dataset. Overall, the number of items per area after the cleaning operations decreased from 739 to 472 with a density of 20620.48 items/km² (2.06 items/100m²) and 12226.15 items/km² (1.22 items/100m²), respectively. This improvement is certainly related to the cleaning operations, as we will see below. However, some items may have been buried by sediments or been displaced by currents and therefore not been detected by the MBES.

In fact, the comparative temporal analysis between the data from May 2022 and May 2023 revealed significant dynamics, including the displacement of debris due to currents or nautical activities and the disappearance of other objects following the cleaning operations. For example, several metallic fragments shifted locations within the area, while lighter objects such as plastic parts were more likely to be transported out of the mapped zone. However, the results for the mapped items for May 2023 show again an increase of the density, and a decrease after the second cleaning campaign in December 2023. These findings underline both the complexity of the marine litter problem and the effectiveness of repeated clean-up efforts in mitigating its impact, but also the need to reduce pollution at the source.

Figure 25 - Example of a shifted object detected during the mapping surveys performed in May 2022 and May 2023.

MAELSTROM

Out of the full area mapped with the MBES, a smaller area was selected to map in detail the result of the cleaning operations (red box in Figure 24 and Figure 26). In this area, a total of 126 objects were counted in May 2022, while in November 2022 (after the cleaning) only 51 objects were mapped. The comparison between the two maps clearly shows the disappearance of the objects removed by the Seabed Cleaning Platform (Figure 26, down).

Figure 26 - Map of the area selected for the cleaning operations in May 2022 (up) and November 2022 (down).

During the first Sacca Fisola clean-up campaign, conducted between 15 and 27 September 2022, a significant number of marine debris of various types was collected. Among the items recovered were a wooden panel, a rope, a coiled steel cable, several bricks, a plastic net, a steel bar, a trolley, part of a steel wagon, glass bottles, a Venetian cart, twelve truck tyres, a five-metre-long aluminium roof panel, and a steel roll bar. Other materials included plastic sheets, textile, numerous plastic fragments, aluminium cans, an electronic circuit board, a steel and concrete block, wood, electric cables, and steel frames (Figure 27).

The cleanup covered a total area of 1193 m², achieving an estimated efficiency of 59%. This value reflects the ability of the robotic platform to tackle marine litter effectively, while also highlighting the challenges posed by the very low visibility and heavily anthropized environment of Sacca Fisola. The proximity of a municipal waste collection point contributes significantly to the continuous accumulation of debris in the lagoon. In this area, the cable robot could rely almost only to the bathymetric data since the cameras were under performing due to high water turbidity and low visibility.

Figure 27 - Images of marine waste recovery operations during the Sacca Fisola clean-up campaigns: a. Recovery of a piece of steel machinery; b. Removal of a tyre; c. Removal of a 5-metre-long aluminium cover panel; d. Mixed waste collected, including plastic fragments, aluminium cans and an electronic circuit board. These pictures highlight the variety of materials recovered.

During the second cleaning campaign, conducted on 1 and 2 June 2023, the robotic platform employed its grab bucket to collect marine litter in four specific locations

within the designated cleaning area at Sacca Fisola. A total of 197 objects were removed, including items such as glass, plastic, metal, and mixed materials. The use of the grab bucket allowed for the efficient collection of larger objects and fragments that were distributed across the cleaning area. Some items, such as metal fragments or small pieces of plastic, were not easily detectable with the MBES but were successfully located and removed thanks to the platform's direct intervention.

5.2.1.2 Coastal site: abandoned mussel farm

The cleaning operations carried out in the abandoned mussel farm yielded significant results, both in terms of the length of ropes removed and the total number of objects successfully eliminated (Figure 28).

The operations on 6 and 7 June 2023 removed mussel farm waste, ropes and buoys. On 6 June, the first operation successfully removed an entire rope, while the second operation involved cutting and extracting another rope to ensure its complete removal. On 7 June, the first operation removed a single rope, while the second focused on an assembly of ropes and a 125 x 61 cm buoy. With the help of the Venice State Police Diving Unit, it was also possible to remove two other buoys floating in the water column, identified thanks to the MBES.

Figure 28 - Images of the mussel farm clean-up using the robotic seabed cleaning platform: a. Real-time monitoring of the seabed with identification of debris such as ropes and nets; b. Use of the robotic platform to recover debris from the seabed; c. Recovery of ropes and aquaculture equipment, including a float; d. A removed plastic buoy colonized by biological communities (fouling communities) that were sampled for further taxonomic analyses.

Although four ropes were removed, the post-cleaning MBES mapping showed the presence of three ropes instead of the expected two (Figure 29). This discrepancy can be explained by the fact that one of the ropes was partially cut off during removal, leaving a small part on the seafloor. Furthermore, although there are four removal points corresponding to the harvested tops, their positions on the map do not coincide with the original ones. This is due to the fact that the divers bundled the ropes together during the operations to facilitate their removal from the platform.

Figure 29 - The images show the mapped objects on the seafloor (purple and blue lines for ropes and red points of buoys in the water column): a) before and b) after the cleaning and removal of marine litter in the specific cleaning area (black box) at the abandoned mussel farm.

Within the sub-area where the seabed cleaning platform operated, the ropes present on the seafloor were reduced from an initial length of 404 metres in 2022 to 126 metres in 2023, representing a **removal rate of 69%**. However, an additional rope segment was removed outside the cleaning area. Thus, the total initial rope length interested by the cleaning was of 514 metres, which was reduced to 126 metres, resulting in an **effective removal rate of 75%**. These lengths were calculated by integrating the segments obtained from the bathymetric data with the length calculation tools in ArcGIS Pro.

In terms of object removal, the total number of items decreased from 9 (3 buoys and 6 ropes) to 3 ropes, as all buoys were successfully removed. This equates to an **overall removal rate of 67%**, leaving only 33% of the original objects in the area. These results highlight the effectiveness of the clean-up operations and underscore the importance of targeted interventions in addressing marine debris accumulation.

Chemical analysis of the collected ropes identified the material as polyamide 6 (PA6), also known as nylon. This semi-crystalline polymer is robust, has excellent abrasion

and chemical resistance, and a density of 1.14 g/cm³. The total weight of the collected ropes was 260 kg (± 10 kg).

Bathymetric data analysis further revealed that the total length of ropes within, and in part outside, the operational area was 514 metres. Assuming a diameter of 2.5 cm, the estimated mass of the ropes based on the MBES data corresponded to approximately 287 kg of polyamide 6, aligning closely with the measured weight of the collected ropes. These results demonstrate that multibeam data are not only effective for accurately georeferencing objects on the seabed but also valuable for estimating their physical characteristics, such as weight and size.

5.2.1.3 Monitoring the Canal Grande seafloor marine litter hotspot (2013 vs 2023)

The comparison of the data collected in the Canal Grande in 2013 and 2023 (Figure 30) shows a significant increase in both the total number of objects mapped and the density of marine debris. In 2013, the total number of objects detected was 255 in the surveyed area, corresponding to a density of 8,822.10 items/km². In 2023, after ten years, the total number of objects had increased to 775 with a density of 26,812.27 items/km², an **increase of more than 200%** in the total number of objects.

Figure 30 - Monitoring of seafloor marine litter in the Gran Canal in 2013 (top) and 2023 (bottom).

A typological analysis of the waste based on the MBES data showed that tyres were the most represented category in both years, increasing from 103 items (40.39%) in 2013

to 389 items (50.19%) in 2023, an increase of 277.67%. The unknown category, which includes unidentifiable objects, also showed significant growth, rising from 142 objects (55.69%) in 2013 to 347 (44.77%) in 2023 (+144.37%). Other categories, such as poles, showed an increase of 311.11%, but represent a smaller percentage of the total. Finally, the category of wrecks increases from one object in 2013 to two in 2023.

This overall increase could be attributed to a combination of factors, including the intensification of maritime traffic, the increase in economic activities in the area and the lack of effective waste management policies over the years. The progressive accumulation of litter on the seabed suggests the importance of targeted interventions to identify the main sources of pollution and reduce the marine litter burden in the area. The increase in more persistent categories, such as tyres, also underlines the need for specific management of this type of material, which remains a major problem for the health of the ecosystem.

5.2.2 Assessment of the biological community

5.2.2.1 Soft bottom macrozoobenthos

Lagoon site: Sacca Fisola

In total, 2705 individuals (including integer colonies of colonial taxa) were analyzed during the 4 monitoring campaigns conducted in the years 2023 and 2024, leading to the identification of 129 taxa at the species level or the highest possible taxonomic resolution. Species belongs to the following phyla: Annelida (class Polychaeta), Arthropoda (Decapoda, Amphipoda, Cumacea, Isopoda, Tanaidacea and Ostracoda), Bryozoa, Cnidaria (order Actiniaria), Echinodermata (classes Asterozoa, Holothurozoa and Ophiurozoa), Mollusca (classes Bivalvia and Gastropoda), Porifera and Tunicata (class Ascidiacea). The data for each of the individual campaigns are as follows: 2023 1st campaign 492 individuals (50 taxa), 2nd campaign 942 individuals (66 taxa); 2024 1st campaign 363 individuals (55 taxa), 2nd campaign 908 individuals (52 taxa). The total list of taxa identified, 2002 pre-cleaning monitoring included, is shown in Annex 1.

The composition of the community in terms of % distribution of abundances among the major taxonomic groups (with polychaetes divided into "errantia" and "sedentaria", group of functional interest but whose systematic use is debated) is presented in Figure 31 for each replicate. Polychaeta errantia and sedentaria, as well

as Amphipoda and Bivalvia dominates. The overall structure appears to be characterized by noteworthy variability between campaigns and stations.

Figure 31 - Lagoon site: Percentage distribution of abundances among the major taxonomic groups for each replicate (A.C. = Animalia Caetera)

Main univariate descriptors of macrozoobenthos community are summarized in Table 8, and include density, number of taxa, Shannon diversity, AMBI (BC) and M-AMBI, for each station and monitoring campaign since the 2022 pre-cleaning campaign.

Table 8 – Lagoon site: main univariate ecological descriptors of macrozoobenthos community for each monitoring campaign and station (mean and standard deviation).

campaign	year, season	station	metric	mean	sd
1	2022, spring	LV1	S	22	5.568
1	2022, spring	LV1	H'	2.429	0.141
1	2022, spring	LV1	BC	2.523	0.151
1	2022, spring	LV1	M-AMBI	0.609	0.036
1	2022, spring	LV1	dens. N/m ²	1793.333	516.753
1	2022, spring	LV2	S	26	5.292
1	2022, spring	LV2	H'	3.055	0.882
1	2022, spring	LV2	BC	1.347	0.907

<i>campaign</i>	<i>year, season</i>	<i>station</i>	<i>metric</i>	<i>mean</i>	<i>sd</i>
1	2022, spring	LV2	M-AMBI	0.775	0.03
1	2022, spring	LV2	dens. N/m ²	1736.667	1317.662
2	2023, spring	LV1	S	20.333	4.933
2	2023, spring	LV1	H'	2.801	0.282
2	2023, spring	LV1	BC	3.061	0.266
2	2023, spring	LV1	M-AMBI	0.589	0.045
2	2023, spring	LV1	dens. N/m ²	1410	313.209
2	2023, spring	LV2	S	10.333	5.508
2	2023, spring	LV2	H'	2.721	0.826
2	2023, spring	LV2	BC	2.065	0.289
2	2023, spring	LV2	M-AMBI	0.583	0.094
2	2023, spring	LV2	dens. N/m ²	230	90
3	2023, autumn	LV1	S	35.667	1.155
3	2023, autumn	LV1	H'	3.801	0.593
3	2023, autumn	LV1	BC	2.271	0.153
3	2023, autumn	LV1	M-AMBI	0.839	0.065
3	2023, autumn	LV1	dens. N/m ²	2493.333	490.544
3	2023, autumn	LV2	S	15.333	4.041
3	2023, autumn	LV2	H'	2.742	1.017
3	2023, autumn	LV2	BC	1.943	0.243
3	2023, autumn	LV2	M-AMBI	0.629	0.097
3	2023, autumn	LV2	dens. N/m ²	646.667	158.85
4	2024, spring	LV1	S	23	6.928
4	2024, spring	LV1	H'	3.87	0.428
4	2024, spring	LV1	BC	2.38	0.448
4	2024, spring	LV1	M-AMBI	0.746	0.099
4	2024, spring	LV1	dens. N/m ²	743.333	293.995
4	2024, spring	LV2	S	12.667	2.082
4	2024, spring	LV2	H'	2.714	0.336
4	2024, spring	LV2	BC	1.894	0.185
4	2024, spring	LV2	M-AMBI	0.611	0.017
4	2024, spring	LV2	dens. N/m ²	466.667	102.144
5	2024, autumn	LV1	S	32.667	2.887
5	2024, autumn	LV1	H'	4.12	0.215
5	2024, autumn	LV1	BC	2.57	0.321

<i>campaign</i>	<i>year, season</i>	<i>station</i>	<i>metric</i>	<i>mean</i>	<i>sd</i>
5	2024, autumn	LV1	M-AMBI	0.822	0.061
5	2024, autumn	LV1	dens. N/m ²	2463.333	964.642
5	2024, autumn	LV2	S	16.333	1.528
5	2024, autumn	LV2	H'	3.403	0.299
5	2024, autumn	LV2	BC	1.868	0.239
5	2024, autumn	LV2	M-AMBI	0.696	0.044
5	2024, autumn	LV2	dens. N/m ²	563.333	15.275

Coastal site: abandoned mussel farm

In total, 4887 individuals (including integer colonies of colonial taxa) were analyzed during the 4 monitoring campaigns conducted in the years 2023 and 2024, leading to the identification of 167 taxa at the species level or the highest possible taxonomic resolution. Species belongs to the following phyla: Annelida (class Polychaeta, including Sipuncula), Arthropoda (Pycnogonida, Decapoda, Amphipoda, Cumacea, Isopoda and Tanaidacea), Bryozoa, Echinodermata (classes Asterozoa, Echinozoa, and Ophiurozoa), Mollusca (classes Bivalvia, Gastropoda and Scaphopoda), Nemertea (class Anopla) and Platyhelminthes.

The data for each of the individual campaigns are as follows: 2023 1st campaign 842 individuals (76 taxa), 2nd campaign 1594 individuals (95 taxa); 2024 1st campaign 726 individuals (68 taxa), 2nd campaign 1725 individuals (104 taxa). The total list of taxa identified, 2002 pre-cleaning monitoring included is shown in Annex 1.

The composition of the community in terms of % distribution of abundances among the major taxonomic groups (with polychaetes divided into "errantia" and "sedentaria", group of functional interest but whose systematic use is debated) is presented in Figure 32 for each replicate. Polychaeta errantia and sedentaria, as well as Echinodermata and Bivalvia dominates. The overall structure appears to be less variable than for the Lagoon site.

Figure 32 - Coastal site: percentage distribution of abundances among the major taxonomic groups for each replicate (A.C. = Animalia Caetera).

Main univariate descriptors of macrozoobenthos community are summarized in Table 9, including density, number of taxa, Shannon diversity, AMBI (BC) and M-AMBI, for each station and monitoring campaign since the 2022 pre-cleaning campaign.

Table 9 - Coastal site: main univariate ecological descriptors of macrozoobenthos community for each monitoring campaign and station (mean and standard deviation).

campaign	year, season	station	metric	mean	sd
1	2022, spring	CS1	S	38.667	0.577
1	2022, spring	CS1	H'	4.062	0.018
1	2022, spring	CS1	BC	1.974	0.18
1	2022, spring	CS1	M-AMBI	0.758	0.014
1	2022, spring	CS1	dens. N/m ²	2016.667	540.123
1	2022, spring	CS2	S	39	4.583
1	2022, spring	CS2	H'	4.221	0.032
1	2022, spring	CS2	BC	1.575	0.175
1	2022, spring	CS2	M-AMBI	0.802	0.019
1	2022, spring	CS2	dens. N/m ²	1950	311.769
2	2023, spring	CS1	S	29.667	3.786
2	2023, spring	CS1	H'	3.915	0.284

<i>campaign</i>	<i>year, season</i>	<i>station</i>	<i>metric</i>	<i>mean</i>	<i>sd</i>
2	2023, spring	CS1	BC	2.039	0.61
2	2023, spring	CS1	M-AMBI	0.709	0.069
2	2023, spring	CS1	dens. N/m ²	1193.333	37.859
2	2023, spring	CS2	S	37.333	3.055
2	2023, spring	CS2	H'	4.109	0.217
2	2023, spring	CS2	BC	1.808	0.169
2	2023, spring	CS2	M-AMBI	0.769	0.014
2	2023, spring	CS2	dens. N/m ²	1613.333	178.979
3	2023, autumn	CS2	S	52.667	4.041
3	2023, autumn	CS2	H'	4.562	0.275
3	2023, autumn	CS2	BC	2.28	0.202
3	2023, autumn	CS2	M-AMBI	0.824	0.035
3	2023, autumn	CS2	dens. N/m ²	2743.333	804.135
3	2023, autumn	CS4	S	47.333	10.408
3	2023, autumn	CS4	H'	4.463	0.253
3	2023, autumn	CS4	BC	2.139	0.102
3	2023, autumn	CS4	M-AMBI	0.808	0.044
3	2023, autumn	CS4	dens. N/m ²	2570	946.361
4	2024, spring	CS2	S	31.667	4.509
4	2024, spring	CS2	H'	3.762	0.224
4	2024, spring	CS2	BC	2.149	0.124
4	2024, spring	CS2	M-AMBI	0.696	0.031
4	2024, spring	CS2	dens. N/m ²	1313.333	223.681
4	2024, spring	CS4	S	26	7
4	2024, spring	CS4	H'	3.637	0.382
4	2024, spring	CS4	BC	2.017	0.282
4	2024, spring	CS4	M-AMBI	0.676	0.06
4	2024, spring	CS4	dens. N/m ²	1106.667	288.675
5	2024, autumn	CS2	S	63.333	10.017
5	2024, autumn	CS2	H'	4.764	0.275
5	2024, autumn	CS2	BC	2.003	0.198
5	2024, autumn	CS2	M-AMBI	0.9	0.056
5	2024, autumn	CS2	dens. N/m ²	3583.333	604.345
5	2024, autumn	CS4	S	52	4.359
5	2024, autumn	CS4	H'	4.813	0.162

<i>campaign</i>	<i>year, season</i>	<i>station</i>	<i>metric</i>	<i>mean</i>	<i>sd</i>
5	2024, autumn	CS4	BC	1.945	0.296
5	2024, autumn	CS4	M-AMBI	0.866	0.04
5	2024, autumn	CS4	dens. N/m ²	2166.667	203.06

5.2.2.2 Litter fouling community

The fouling community collected from marine litter items was analyzed for both sites on a limited number of items (five from the cleaning of the Lagoon site and three from the coastal site). In Annex the lists of the taxa recorded is listed. Table 10 presents the main univariate descriptors of the community, calculated on abundances. However, based on the limited number of samples and the variety of substrates analyzed in terms of shape, material, exposure and degree of preservation, the main focus of the analysis is meant to be the contribution to overall macrozoobenthos diversity in the sites.

In total, 1939 individuals (including integer colonies of colonial taxa) were analyzed from five marine litter items collected in the lagoon site and 5138 from three marine litter items collected in the coastal site, leading to the identification of 69 and 58 taxa, respectively. Overall, 109 taxa were identified (the two sites sharing very few species) belonging to the following phyla: Annelida (class Polychaeta), Arthropoda (Decapoda, Amphipoda, Isopoda and Balanidae), Bryozoa, Cnidaria (orders Actinaria and Zoanthidea), Echinodermata (classes Asterozoa and Ophiurozoa), Mollusca (classes Bivalvia and Gastropoda), Porifera and Tunicata (class Ascidiacea). In the lagoon site all the recorded soft bottom macrozoobenthos and fouling share 38 taxa, with 31 taxa exclusive to the fouling, whereas in the coastal site all the recorded soft bottom macrozoobenthos and fouling share only 27 taxa, with 31 taxa exclusive to the fouling.

Table 10 – Main univariate ecological descriptors of macrozoobenthos community from marine litter fouling for both lagoon and coastal site (mean and standard deviation).

site	N. replicates	metric	mean	sd
LV	5	S	33.20	6.94
LV	5	H'	3.53	0.37
LV	5	BC	2.48	0.37
LV	5	M-AMBI	0.86	0.09
LV	5	dens. N/m ²	3878.00	1805.98
CS	3	S	35.67	19.21
CS	3	H'	3.17	1.58
CS	3	BC	2.33	1.73
CS	3	M-AMBI	0.86	0.43
CS	3	dens. N/m ²	17126.67	8439.97

5.2.2.3 Monitoring of the fish community through sampling campaigns

Lagoon site: Sacca Fisola

At Sacca Fisola, after the cleaning operation carried out by the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in September 2022, the fish fauna community was monitored in spring and autumn both in 2023 and 2024.

During the first post cleaning monitoring campaign carried out in spring 2023, the nets were positioned on the seabed of the shallow waters for 5 days. After being hauled out 12 fish species were recorded, with a total of 586 individuals and 6202.43 g of biomass. The abundance and biomass data are shown in Table 11.

Table 11 - Lagoon Site: abundance and biomass data of fish fauna collected by each fike net in spring 2023.

Species	Fike net N°	Abundance (N° of individuals)	Biomass (total weight g)
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	1	25	54.5
<i>Solea solea</i>	1	1	61.33
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	1	3	101.61
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	1	2	84.5
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	1	2	119
<i>Hippocampus guttulatus</i>	1	1	9.2

Species	Fike net N°	Abundance (N° of individuals)	Biomass (total weight g)
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	2	13	28.34
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	2	2	67.74
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	4	4	135.48
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	4	1	59.5
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	4	1	97
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	4	92	200
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	5	8	270.96
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	5	138	300
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	5	1	395
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	5	4	238
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	5	1	143
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	6	10	338.7
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	6	69	150
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	6	1	136
<i>Syngnathus acus</i>	6	1	22
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	6	1	59.5
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	7	1	450
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	7	1	59.5
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	7	46	100
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	7	7	237.09
<i>Solea solea</i>	7	1	61.33
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	7	1	42.25
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	8	5	169.35
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	8	7	416.5
<i>Solea solea</i>	8	1	61.33
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	8	69	150
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	9	46	100
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	9	9	304.83
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	9	4	169
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	9	4	238
<i>Chelon labrosus</i>	9	1	420
<i>Pomatoschistus marmoratus</i>	9	1	1.89
<i>Symphodus melops</i>	9	1	150

During the second post cleaning monitoring campaign carried out in autumn 2023, the nets were positioned on the seabed of the shallow waters for 5 days. After being

hauled out a total of 17 fish species were recorded, with a total of 562 individuals and 11517 g of biomass. The abundance and biomass data are shown in Table 12.

Table 12 - Lagoon Site: abundance and biomass data of fish fauna collected by each fike net in autumn 2023.

Species	Fike net N°	Abundance (N° of individuals)	Biomass (total weight g)
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	1	135	320
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	1	1	20
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	1	4	160
<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>	2	1	320
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	2	84	200
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	2	1	5
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	3	1	60
<i>Gobius niger</i>	3	2	13
<i>Hippocampus guttulatus</i>	3	1	3
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	3	4	25
<i>Solea solea</i>	3	3	65
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	3	1	90
<i>Syngnathus acus</i>	3	1	15
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	3	39	2100
<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>	4	1	60
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	4	12	28
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	4	1	40
<i>Gobius niger</i>	4	1	6
<i>Gobius paganellus</i>	4	1	5
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	4	1	8
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	4	4	130
<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>	5	1	130
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	5	34	80
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	5	3	340
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	5	1	220
<i>Gobius niger</i>	5	3	21
<i>Gobius paganellus</i>	5	1	50
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	5	3	35
<i>Solea solea</i>	5	1	100
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	5	2	190
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	5	31	3300

Species	Fike net N°	Abundance (N° of individuals)	Biomass (total weight g)
<i>Gobius niger</i>	6	1	8
<i>Gobius paganellus</i>	6	2	11
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	6	5	23
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	6	21	1200
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	7	38	90
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	7	1	2
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	8	2	470
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	8	5	120
<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>	9	4	1020
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	9	63	150
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	9	1	40
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	9	1	85
<i>Pomatoschistus marmoratus</i>	9	15	17
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	10	12	29
<i>Chelon saliens</i>	10	1	10
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	10	1	80
<i>Pomatoschistus marmoratus</i>	10	8	9
<i>Pomatoschistus minutus</i>	10	1	4
<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	10	1	10

During the third post cleaning monitoring campaign carried out in spring 2024, the nets were positioned on the seabed of the shallow waters for 9 days. After being hauled out a total of 11 fish species were recorded, with a total of 68 individuals corresponding to a biomass of 3252g. The abundance and biomass data are shown in Table 13.

Table 13 - Lagoon Site: abundance and biomass data of fish fauna collected by each fike net in spring 2024.

Species	Fike net N°	Abundance (N° of individuals)	Biomass (total weight g)
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	1	5	12
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	1	2	310
<i>Gobius niger</i>	1	1	80
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	1	2	18
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	1	2	180
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	1	2	16

Species	Fike net N°	Abundance (N° of individuals)	Biomass (total weight g)
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	2	1	60
<i>Hippocampus hippocampus</i>	2	1	80
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	2	3	28
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	2	1	70
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	2	12	210
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	3	4	100
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	4	1	120
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	4	2	160
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	4	1	12
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	5	1	140
<i>Hippocampus hippocampus</i>	5	2	14
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	5	1	6
<i>Solea solea</i>	5	1	30
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	5	2	120
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	5	1	80
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	6	1	80
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	6	3	200
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	6	1	140
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	6	1	8
<i>Chelon labrosus</i>	7	1	60
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	7	1	250
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	7	5	300
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	7	2	8
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	8	1	60
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	9	4	300

During the fourth post cleaning monitoring campaign carried out in autumn 2024, the nets were positioned in the seabed of the shallow waters for 1 days. After being hauled out a total of 13 fish species were recorded, with a total of 64 individuals corresponding to a biomass of 1969 g. The abundance and biomass data are shown in Table 14.

Table 14 - Lagoon Site: abundance and biomass data of fish fauna collected by each fike net in spring 2024.

Species	Fike net N°	Abundance (N° of individuals)	Biomass (total weight g)
<i>Gobius paganellus</i>	1	4	89.6

Species	Fike net N°	Abundance (N° of individuals)	Biomass (total weight g)
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	1	1	5
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	1	2	70.8
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	2	2	4
<i>Solea solea</i>	2	1	5
<i>Syngnathus typhle</i>	2	1	1
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	3	1	5
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	3	1	90
<i>Syngnathus typhle</i>	3	1	1
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	3	5	150
<i>Chelon saliens</i>	4	1	70.1
<i>Gobius paganellus</i>	5	6	134.4
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	5	1	5
<i>Syngnathus abaster</i>	5	1	1
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	5	1	6.5
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	6	1	56.8
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	7	1	5
<i>Solea solea</i>	7	4	130
<i>Boops boops</i>	8	1	55
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	8	11	520
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	9	3	90
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	10	6	13.8
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	10	8	460

In Table 15 and Table 16 the average catch per unit effort (CPUE) values of abundance and biomass were reported for each lagoon species found during the post cleaning campaigns.

Table 15 - CPUE mean values (and standard deviations) calculated in terms of abundance (individuals/fike net day) for each lagoon species sampled during 2023 and 2024 campaigns.

Family	Species	CPUE (n° individuals/fike net die)			
		Spring 2023	Autumn 2023	Spring 2023	Autumn 2024
Anguillidae	<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>	0	0.14 (0.25)	0	0 (0)
Atherinidae	<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	9.96 (8.76)	7.56 (8.91)	0.06 (0.18)	0.8 (1.93)
Blenniidae	<i>Salaria pavo</i>	0	0.32 (0.36)	0.07 (0.12)	0.4 (0.52)
Carangidae	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0	0	0.02 (0.05)	0.1 (0.32)
Clupeidae	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0	0.02 (0.06)	0	0 (0)
Gobiidae	<i>Gobius niger</i>	0	0.14 (0.21)	0.01 (0.04)	0 (0)
Gobiidae	<i>Gobius paganellus</i>	0	0.08 (0.14)	0	1 (2.16)
Gobiidae	<i>Knipowitschia panizzae</i>	0	0	0	0 (0)
Gobiidae	<i>Pomatoschistus marmoratus</i>	0.02 (0.06)	0.46 (1.02)	0	0 (0)
Gobiidae	<i>Pomatoschistus minutus</i>	0	0.02 (0.06)	0	0 (0)
Gobiidae	<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	0.96 (0.72)	2.08 (2.9)	0.24 (0.41)	2.1 (3.57)
Labridae	<i>Symphodus melops</i>	0.02 (0.06)	0	0	0 (0)
Labridae	<i>Symphodus roissali</i>	0	0	0	0 (0)
Moronidae	<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	0.04 (0.08)	0.1 (0.14)	0	0 (0)
Mugilidae	<i>Chelon auratus</i>	0.4 (0.46)	0.1 (0.19)	0.01 (0.04)	0.8 (2.53)
Mugilidae	<i>Chelon labrosus</i>	0.02 (0.06)	0	0.01 (0.04)	0 (0)
Mugilidae	<i>Chelon ramada</i>	0.16 (0.26)	0.02 (0.06)	0.07 (0.08)	0.1 (0.32)
Mugilidae	<i>Chelon saliens</i>	0	0.02 (0.06)	0	0.1 (0.32)

Family	Species	CPUE (n° individuals/fike net die)			
		Spring 2023	Autumn 2023	Spring 2023	Autumn 2024
Soleidae	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.06 (0.1)	0.08 (0.19)	0.01 (0.04)	0.5 (1.27)
Sparidae	<i>Boops boops</i>	0	0	0	0.1 (0.32)
Sparidae	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	0.04 (0.08)	0.06 (0.13)	0.22 (0.18)	0.1 (0.32)
Syngnathid ae	<i>Hippocampus guttulatus</i>	0.02 (0.06)	0.02 (0.06)	0	0 (0)
Syngnathid ae	<i>Hippocampus hippocampus</i>	0	0	0.03 (0.07)	0 (0)
Syngnathid ae	<i>Syngnathus abaster</i>	0	0	0	0.1 (0.32)
Syngnathid ae	<i>Syngnathus acus</i>	0.02 (0.06)	0.02 (0.06)	0	0 (0)
Syngnathid ae	<i>Syngnathus typhle</i>	0	0	0	0.2 (0.42)

Table 16 - CPUE mean values (and standard deviations) calculated in terms of biomass (grams/ fikenet day) for each lagoon species sampled during 2023 and 2024 campaigns.

Family	Species	CPUE (g/fikenet die)			
		Spring 2023	Autumn 2023	Spring 2023	Autumn 2024
Anguillidae	<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>	0	30.6 (64.26)	0	0 (0)
Atherinidae	<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	21.66 (19.03)	17.94 (21.14)	0.13 (0.42)	1.78 (4.41)
Blenniidae	<i>Salaria pavo</i>	0	2.36 (2.56)	0.58 (1.09)	2 (2.58)
Carangidae	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0	0	2.44 (5.39)	0.65 (2.06)
Clupeidae	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0	0.2 (0.63)	0	0 (0)

Family	Species	CPUE (g/fikenet die)			
		Spring 2023	Autumn 2023	Spring 2023	Autumn 2024
Gobiidae	<i>Gobius niger</i>	0	0.96 (1.46)	0.89 (2.81)	0 (0)
Gobiidae	<i>Gobius paganellus</i>	0	1.32 (3.13)	0	22.4 (48.39)
Gobiidae	<i>Knipowitschia panizzae</i>	0	0	0	0 (0)
Gobiidae	<i>Pomatoschistus marmoratus</i>	0.04 (0.12)	0.52 (1.16)	0	0 (0)
Gobiidae	<i>Pomatoschistus minutus</i>	0	0.08 (0.25)	0	0 (0)
Gobiidae	<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	32.52 (24.49)	140.2 (229.81)	3.93 (7.6)	83.08 (162.27)
Labridae	<i>Symphodus melops</i>	3 (9.49)	0	0	0 (0)
Labridae	<i>Symphodus roissali</i>	0	0	0	0 (0)
Moronidae	<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	10.94 (28.44)	13.9 (29.05)	0	0 (0)
Mugilidae	<i>Chelon auratus</i>	23.8 (27.48)	8.4 (21.2)	0.89 (2.81)	46 (145.46)
Mugilidae	<i>Chelon labrosus</i>	8.4 (26.56)	0	0.67 (2.11)	0 (0)
Mugilidae	<i>Chelon ramada</i>	13.82 (25.46)	4.4 (13.91)	9.78 (12.76)	5.68 (17.96)
Mugilidae	<i>Chelon saliens</i>	0	0.2 (0.63)	0	7.01 (22.17)
Soleidae	<i>Solea solea</i>	3.68 (5.93)	3.3 (7.15)	0.33 (1.05)	13.5 (40.96)
Sparidae	<i>Boops boops</i>	0	0	0	5.5 (17.39)
Sparidae	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	5.58 (11.77)	5.6 (12.71)	15.44 (12.15)	9 (28.46)

Family	Species	CPUE (g/fikenet die)			
		Spring 2023	Autumn 2023	Spring 2023	Autumn 2024
Syngnathidae	<i>Hippocampus guttulatus</i>	0.18 (0.58)	0.06 (0.19)	0	0 (0)
Syngnathidae	<i>Hippocampus hippocampus</i>	0	0	1.04 (2.8)	0 (0)
Syngnathidae	<i>Syngnathus abaster</i>	0	0	0	0.1 (0.32)
Syngnathidae	<i>Syngnathus acus</i>	0.44 (1.39)	0.3 (0.95)	0	0 (0)
Syngnathidae	<i>Syngnathus typhle</i>	0	0	0	0.2 (0.42)

The standardized data showed that the lagoon fish community monitored during 2023 and 2024 campaigns was generally characterized by the presence of *Atherina boyeri*, *Zosterisessor ophiocephalus*, *Chelon auratus*, *Chelon ramada* and *Solea solea*, which were found in all campaigns and showed wide seasonal and annual variability both in abundance and biomass values.

Some species were observed only during 2023 campaigns (*Anguilla anguilla*, *Sardina pilchardus*, *Pomatoschistus marmoratus*, *Pomatoschistus minutus*, *Symphodus melops*, *Dicentrarchus labrax*, *Hippocampus guttulatus*, *Syngnathus acus*) and others only in 2024 campaigns (*Trachurus trachurus*, *Boops boops* and *Syngnathus abaster*).

The data related to the number of species and individuals, Shannon diversity index and Margalef richness index are reported in Table 17.

The number of species resulted quite similar in spring 2023 and in 2024, ranging from 11 to 13, whereas the value resulted higher in autumn 2023 (17). Both Shannon and Margalef indices were progressively higher in 2024 than in 2023, reaching the values of 2.05 and 2.89 in autumn 2024, respectively.

Table 17 - Biodiversity indices of lagoon area fish community.

LAGOON AREA	Spring 2023	Autumn 2023	Spring 2023	Autumn 2024
Species (n°)	12	17	11	13
Shannon (H')	0.64	1.17	1.83	2.05
Margalef (D)	1.73	2.53	2.37	2.89

The data underlined how the lagoon fish communities are inherently characterized by high interannual variability, mainly related to environmental variability. Their structure and species composition may therefore be subject to even major variations from year to year, and only medium- to long-term monitoring will be able to identify any changing trends.

Coastal site: abandoned mussel farm

During the second pre-cleaning monitoring campaign of fish community, which was carried out in spring 2023, a total of 12 specimens belonging to 6 different species were collected (Table 18). A specimen of *Merlangius merlangus* was found partially in carcass form due to the presence of saprophagous isopods.

Most of the catches were taken using 33 mm trammel nets and 40 mm gillnets.

Table 18 - Coastal Site: abundance and biomass data of fish fauna collected in each station in spring 2023.

Species	Sampling station	Fishing net	Abundance (N° of individuals)	Biomass (Total weight g)
<i>Solea solea</i>	S1	40 mm gillnet	1	148
<i>Spicara maena</i>	S1	33 mm trammel net	1	58
<i>Umbrina cirrhosa</i>	S1	33 mm trammel net	4	518
<i>Chelidonichthys lucerna</i>	S2	40 mm gillnet	1	168
<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>	S2	40 mm gillnet	1	32*
<i>Gobius niger</i>	S3	trap	1	28
<i>Solea solea</i>	S3	40 mm gillnet	1	242

MAELSTROM

<i>Chelidonichthys lucerna</i>	S4	50 mm gillnet	1	86
<i>Solea solea</i>	S4	33 mm trammel net	1	284

*weight is to be considered as indicative as it refers to a preyed specimen

After the cleaning operations carried out by the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in June 2023, the fish fauna community of coastal site was monitored once in 2023 and twice in 2024.

During the first post cleaning monitoring campaign carried out in autumn 2023 a total of 48 specimens belonging to eight different fish species were sampled (*Table 19*). Similarly to previous campaigns, several specimens were found in carcass form due to parasitic and necrophagous activity of isopod crustaceans. Most of the catches were taken using gillnets having 40 and 50 mm mesh size.

Table 19 - Coastal Site: abundance and biomass data of fish fauna collected in each station in autumn 2023.

Species	Sampling station	Fishing net	Abundance (N° of individuals)	Biomass (Total weight g)
<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	S1	32 mm trammel net	1	152
<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	S1	40 mm gillnet	1	166
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S1	50 mm gillnet	2	1534*
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	S1	32 mm trammel net	1	62*
<i>Solea solea</i>	S1	40 mm gillnet	2	316
<i>Umbrina cirrhosa</i>	S1	40 mm gillnet	1	310
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S2	40 mm gillnet	1	1084*
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S2	50 mm gillnet	3	2360*
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	S2	40 mm gillnet	1	70*
<i>Solea solea</i>	S2	40 mm gillnet	4	676
<i>Solea solea</i>	S2	50 mm gillnet	1	320
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	S2	40 mm gillnet	3	176*
<i>Umbrina cirrhosa</i>	S2	32 mm trammel net	1	546*
<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	S3	40 mm gillnet	2	396
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S3	40 mm gillnet	3	3406*
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S3	50 mm gillnet	4	3890*
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	S3	50 mm gillnet	1	492
<i>Solea solea</i>	S3	40 mm gillnet	1	170
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	S3	40 mm gillnet	2	196
<i>Umbrina cirrhosa</i>	S3	50 mm gillnet	2	1162*
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S4	40 mm gillnet	2	1360
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S4	50 mm gillnet	4	2822*
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	S4	40 mm gillnet	1	88*
<i>Scorpaena porcus</i>	S4	40 mm gillnet	1	328
<i>Solea solea</i>	S4	40 mm gillnet	1	234
<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	S4	32 mm trammel net	1	222
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	S4	40 mm gillnet	1	62

*weight is to be considered as indicative as it refers to a parasitized specimen

During the second post cleaning monitoring campaign carried out in spring 2024 a total of 56 specimens belonging to seven different fish species were sampled (Table 20). In contrast to previous campaigns, very few individuals were found in carcass form; two specimens were found without heads. Most of the catches were taken using gillnets having 40 mm mesh size.

Table 20 - Coastal Site: abundance and biomass data of fish fauna collected in each station in spring 2024.

Species	Sampling station	Fishing net	Abundance (N° of individuals)	Biomass (Total weight g)
<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	S1	32 mm trammel net	2	418*
<i>Umbrina cirrhosa</i>	S1	40 mm gillnet	36	7875*
<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	S1	32 mm trammel net	3	314
<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	S1	32 mm trammel net	1	189
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	S2	50 mm gillnet	1	nd*
<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	S3	32 mm trammel net	2	266
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	S3	32 mm trammel net	1	162*
<i>Gobius niger</i>	S3	32 mm trammel net	2	80
<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	S4	40 mm gillnet	1	204
<i>Solea solea</i>	S4	40 mm gillnet	3	564
<i>Umbrina cirrhosa</i>	S4	40 mm gillnet	2	442
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	S4	40 mm gillnet	2	144

* weight is to be considered as indicative as it refers only or also to specimen(s) parasitized by isopods or without head.

During the third post cleaning campaign carried out in Autumn 2024 a total of 71 specimens belonging to eight different fish species were sampled (Table 21). In contrast to previous campaigns, no individuals were found in carcass form. Most of the individuals were caught using 40 mm mesh size gillnets.

Table 21 - Coastal Site: abundance and biomass data of fish fauna collected in each station in Autumn 2024.

Species	Sampling station	Fishing net	Abundance (N° of individuals)	Biomass (Total weight g)
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S1	32	2	1412
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S1	40	13	9838
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S1	50	4	3296
<i>Sarda sarda</i>	S1	32	4	6150
<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	S1	40	1	174
<i>Solea solea</i>	S1	40	2	274
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	S2	32	1	366
<i>Diplodus puntazzo</i>	S2	32	3	494
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S2	50	6	5227
<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	S2	32	1	208
<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	S2	40	2	286
<i>Dentex dentex</i>	S3	32	1	206
<i>Diplodus puntazzo</i>	S3	32	1	180
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S3	50	6	5169
<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	S3	32	2	764
<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	S3	40	3	682
<i>Dentex dentex</i>	S4	32	1	248
<i>Diplodus puntazzo</i>	S4	32	1	192
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S4	50	3	2070
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	S4	32	9	6809
<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	S4	32	1	266
<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	S4	40	1	200
<i>Solea solea</i>	S4	40	3	548

In Table 22 and Table 23 the average catch per unit effort (CPUE) values of abundance and biomass were reported for each marine species found during 2023 and 2024 campaigns.

Table 22 - CPUE mean values (and standard deviations) calculated in terms of abundance (individuals/150 m day) for each marine species sampled during 2023 and 2024 campaign.

Family	Species	CPUE (n° individuals/150m die)			
		Spring 2023	Autumn 2023	Spring 2023	Autumn 2024
Carangidae	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0	1.5 (1.29)	1.0 (0.82)	0
Centracanthidae	<i>Spicara maena</i>	0.25 (0.5)	0	0	0
Gadidae	<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>	0.25 (0.5)	0	0	0
Gobiidae	<i>Gobius niger</i>	0.25 (0.5)**	0	0.5 (1.0)	0
Mugilidae	<i>Chelon auratus</i>	0	0	0	0.25 (0.5)
	<i>Sciaen umbra</i>	0	0.25 (0.5)	0.75 (0.96)	2.5 (2.08)
Sciaenidae	<i>Umbrina cirrhosa</i>	1 (2)	1 (0.82)	9.75 (18.19)	0
Scombridae	<i>Sarda sarda</i>	0	0	0	1 (2)
Scorpaenidae	<i>Scorpaen a porcus</i>	0	0.25 (0.5)	0	0
Scorpaenidae	<i>Scorpaen a scrofa</i>	0	0	0	0.25 (0.5)
Soleidae	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.75 (0.5)	2.25 (1.89)	0.75 (1.5)	1.25 (1.5)
Sparidae	<i>Dentex dentex</i>	0	0	0	0.5 (0.57)

Family	Species	CPUE (n° individuals/150m die)			
		Spring 2023	Autumn 2023	Spring 2023	Autumn 2024
Sparidae	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0	0	0.75 (1.5)	0
Sparidae	<i>Diplodus puntazzo</i>	0	0	0	1.25 (1.25)
Sparidae	<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	0	1 (1.15)	0.75 (0.96)	0
Sparidae	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	0	1 (0)	0	0
Squalidae	<i>Squalus ocanthias</i>	0	0	0	0
Triakidae	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	0	4.75 (2.22)	0	10.75 (6.45)
Triglidae	<i>Chelidoni chthys lucerna</i>	0.5(0.58)	0	0	0

**Values calculated as individuals/taxa day.

Table 23 - CPUE mean values (and standard deviations) calculated in terms of biomass (grams/150 m day) for each marine species sampled during 2023 and 2024 campaign.

Family	Species	CPUE (g/150m die)			
		Spring 2023	Autumn 2023	Spring 2024	Autumn 2024
Carangidae	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0	108.5 (93.3)*	76.5(88.64)*	0
Centrocanthidae	<i>Spicara maena</i>	14.5 (29)	0	0	0
Gadidae	<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>	8 (16)	0	0	0
Gobiidae	<i>Gobius niger</i>	7 (14)**	0	20 (40)	0
Mugilidae	<i>Chelon auratus</i>	0	0	0	183 (91.5)
Sciaenidae	<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	0	55.5 (111)	155 (199.68)*	601.5 (606.88)

Family	Species	CPUE (g/150m die)			
		Spring 2023	Autumn 2023	Spring 2024	Autumn 2024
Sciaenidae	<i>Umbrina cirrhosa</i>	129.5 (259)	504.5 (492)*	2079 (3869,77)*	0
Scombridae	<i>Sarda sarda</i>	0	0	0	1537.5 (3075)
Scorpaenidae	<i>Scorpaena porcus</i>	0	82 (164)	0	0
Scorpaenidae	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	0	0	0	43.5 (87)
Soleidae	<i>Solea solea</i>	168.5 (125.9)	429 (383)	141 (282)	205.5 (262.33)
Sparidae	<i>Dentex dentex</i>	0	0	0	113.5 (132.17)
Sparidae	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0	0	78.5 (157)	0
Sparidae	<i>Diplodus puntazzo</i>	0	0	0	216.5 (204.78)
Sparidae	<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	0	178.5 (208.6)	113.75 (135.05)	0
Sparidae	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	0	178 (210)*	0	0
Squalidae	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	0	0	0	0
Triakidae	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	0	4114 (2397)*	0	8455 (4415.8)
Triglidae	<i>Chelidonich thys lucerna</i>	63.5 (80.6)	0	0	0

*Values indicative as they refer to specimens parasitized by isopods.

**Values calculated as grams/day.

The standardized data showed that the marine fish community monitored during 2023 and 2024 campaigns was generally characterized by the presence of *Solea solea* (found in all campaigns), *Trachurus trachurus* and *Umbrina cirrhosa* which showed particular increase in the number of individuals and biomass during Autumn 2023 and Spring 2024 campaigns as well as *Sciaena umbra* and *Mustelus mustelus* which

increased both in abundance and biomass during the monitoring campaigns, reaching the highest values in Autumn 2024.

The data collected at the marine-coastal site were used to calculate a set of biodiversity indices (number of species, Shannon diversity index and Margalef richness index (Table 24).

The number of species resulted quite similar, ranging from 6 to 8 according to spring and autumn campaigns. No specific annual trends were evident in Shannon and Margalef indices, which ranged from 1.18 to 1.72 and from 1.64 and 3.41, respectively. Notwithstanding, marked seasonal fluctuations were present, mainly linked to environmental variability.

Table 24 - Biodiversity indices of coastal area fish community

COASTAL AREA	Spring 2023	Autumn 2023	Spring 2024	Autumn 2024
Species (n°)	6	8	7	8
Shannon (H')	1.62	1.72	1.18	1.34
Margalef (D)	2.41	1.81	3.41	1.64

5.2.2.4 Monitoring of the fish community through Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM)

Several acoustic signals were detected, analyzed, and categorized. Among the identified species were *Sciaena umbra* and *Umbrina cirrosa* (Figure 33), recognized based on their characteristic vocalizations compared to previous sounds description (Picciulin et al., 2013; Picciulin et al., 2020).

Figure 33 - Spectrograms (below; Hanning window, size = 1024, frequency grid spacing = 5.86 Hz) and waveform (above) produced by *S. umbra* (a) and by *U. cirrosa* (b) recorded at sea.

Two distinct types of pulsed sounds were identified both visually and aurally in the recordings from both years. This sounds primarily differing in their pulse envelope. The first type exhibited the characteristic pulse envelope of the brown meagre (*Sciaena umbra*), featuring a sharp initial increase in acoustic energy, which rapidly decayed, followed by a series of damped amplitude-modulated oscillations (Figure 33a; Parmentier et al., 2018). Consequently, this sound type was considered potentially associated with *S. umbra*. The second type (Figure 33b), by contrast, lacked the initial sharp peak of acoustic energy in its pulse envelope, pulse period was longer, and

number of pulses were reduced compared to *S. umbra*; in its turn this led to assigning the sounds to *U. cirrosa* in accord to Picciulin et al., (2020).

Furthermore, the recordings revealed two other distinct types of biological sounds, possibly produced by two different Crustacean species, which have not been described in the literature so far. The waveform and the spectrogram of these sounds are given in Figure 34.

Figure 34 - Spectrograms (below; Hanning window, size = 1024, frequency grid spacing = 5.86 Hz) and waveform (above) of biological sounds found in the recordings.

Fish vocalizations were successfully recorded in the study area, particularly those emitted by species belonging to the Sciaenidae family. The sounds of *Sciaena umbra* and *Umbrina cirrosa* were clearly identified based on previous descriptions (Picciulin

et al., 2013; Picciulin et al., 2020). Both species are classified as vulnerable due to anthropogenic pressure, habitat degradation, and overfishing (IUCN, 2022).

Sciaena umbra is known for its sedentary and gregarious behavior, primarily inhabiting rocky shelters and exhibiting increased nocturnal activity. Given that the recorded vocalizations coincide with the species' spawning season, these sounds serve as a reproductive function, aligning with findings from other Sciaenidae species). The presence of these fish suggests that the artificial bottom structures within the mussel farm act as a Fish Aggregation Device (FAD), providing essential ecosystem services such as food resources, shelter, and breeding grounds.

Beyond species-specific observations, this study highlights the broader utility of PAM as a powerful tool for marine research and conservation. PAM enables long-term, non-invasive monitoring of species presence and behavior, offering valuable insights into population dynamics and habitat use. This is particularly significant for species classified as vulnerable, such as *S. umbra* and *U. cirrosa*, where continuous data collection can inform and refine conservation strategies. In its turn, this underscores the importance of sustained acoustic monitoring across different years. Such longitudinal studies are crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of conservation measures, detecting population trends, and understanding the impacts of environmental changes on marine biodiversity (Ross et al., 2023). By incorporating PAM into broader marine management frameworks, policymakers and researchers can develop more effective strategies to safeguard vulnerable species and their habitats.

5.2.3 Microplastic assessment

5.2.3.1 Microplastics assessment in surface waters

The environmental parameters recorded during the sampling campaigns for microplastic determinations are listed in the following Table.

Table 25 – Environmental parameters detected during the sampling campaigns.

Station	Sampling date	Probe coord. (Lat)	Probe coord. (Long)	Sea state	Wind force	Wind direction	Temp. (°C)	Salinity (psu)
Sacca Fisola	November 2022	45°25.557'	12.18.433'	0	1	N-NW	n.d.	n.d.
	March 2023	45°25.446'	12°19.231'	1	1	E	11.45	34.24
	October 2023	45°25.502'	12°19.014'	1	1	NE	23.52	34.64
	March 2024	45°25.606'	12°18.379'	1	1	W-NW	n.d.	n.d.
	August 2024	45°25.542'	12°19.030'	0	2	N	n.d.	n.d.
Mussel farm	March 2023	45°27.156'	12°35.690'	0	1	NE	n.d.	n.d.
	October 2023	45°27.089'	12°35.018'	2	0	N	20.55	37.88
	March 2024	45°27.199'	12°35.480'	0	0	-	n.d.	n.d.
	August 2024	45°27.414'	12°35.636'	1	2	N-W	n.d.	n.d.

Lagoon site: Sacca Fisola

The data related to the post-cleaning surveys performed at Sacca Fisola were shown Figure 35 (as mean value and S.E.) and Figure 36 (n. microplastic particles according to shapes and colours).

In November 2022, the microplastics collected a total of 423 particles, with an average concentration of 2.19 ± 0.70 particles m^{-3} (standard error). The dominant fraction is represented by blue irregular fragments, which constitute the largest percentage of the identified particles, followed by transparent flat fragments. In March 2023, a total of 545 microplastic particles were collected with a mean concentration of 2.15 ± 0.27 particles / m^3 . During this survey the predominant microplastics were blue filaments. In October 2023, 275 microplastic particles were collected. The mean concentration observed was 1.49 ± 0.41 particles / m^3 , mostly represented by white irregular fragments. In March 2024, 412 microplastic particles were collected. The mean concentration observed was 1.79 ± 0.88 particles m/ m^3 . As in October, the predominant particles were white irregular fragments. Lastly, in August 2024, 503 microplastic particles were collected with a mean concentration of 3.54 ± 1.97 particles / m^3 , the higher observed during the post-cleaning surveys. Blue filaments were the most common observed microplastic in this survey.

Figure 35 - Floating microplastics (330 µm – 5 mm) detected at Sacca Fisola after the cleaning operations.

Figure 36- Floating microplastics (330 µm – 5 mm) detected at Sacca Fisola after the cleaning operations according to their shapes and colours (sum of the n. of particles found in each replicate for each sample).

As for the particles having a size range from 20 μm to 5 mm (Figure 37 and Figure 38), in March 2023 a total of 516 microplastic particles were collected in 20 litres of surface water, corresponding to a concentration of 25'800 particles / m^3 , the highest concentration observed. The predominant shape was represented by irregular fragments of different colours. In October 2023, 211 microplastic particles were collected, resulting in 10'550 particles / m^3 . Particles were mostly blue filaments and black flat fragments. In March 2024, 202 microplastic particles were collected, resulting in 10'100 particles / m^3 . The predominant colour of the collected microplastics was black and the most common shape was irregular fragments and flat fragments. In August 2024, in total 39 microplastic particles were collected, with a concentration of 1'950 particles / m^3 , the lowest observed, mostly represented by blue filaments.

Figure 37 - Floating microplastics (20 μm – 5 mm) detected at Sacca Fisola after the cleaning operations.

Figure 38- Floating microplastics (20 μm – 5 mm) detected at Sacca Fisola after the cleaning operations according to their shapes and colours (sum of the n. of particles found in each replicate for each sample).

Coastal site: abandoned mussel farm

The data related to the post-cleaning surveys performed at the abandoned mussel farm were shown Figure 39 (as mean value and S.E.) and Figure 40 (n. microplastic particles according to shapes and colours).

In March 2023 (the second pre-cleaning survey at the coastal site), microplastics collected at the abandoned mussel farm showed an average concentration of 1.39 ± 0.21 particles / m^3 . A total of 400 microplastics were detected, classified by colour and shape. The dominant colour was blue, with 209 particles identified, followed by white and transparent. In terms of shape, filaments represented the main fraction with 217 particles, highlighting a possible origin related from ropes or fishing nets. In October 2023, microplastics collected after the cleaning operation showed an average concentration of 0.82 ± 0.05 particles / m^3 . A total of 232 microplastics were detected, classified by colour and shape. The dominant category was blue filaments, as observed also in the previous survey. In March 2024, a total of 251 microplastics were collected corresponding to a concentration of 0.78 ± 0.21 particles m^3 , mostly represented by blue filaments. In August 2024, a total of 193 microplastic particles were collected, with an average concentration of 1.00 ± 0.52 particles m^3 , indicating significant

variability between replicates. The predominant type of microplastic was blue filaments.

Figure 39 - Floating microplastics (330 µm - 5 mm) detected at the abandoned mussel farm before (March 2023) and after the cleaning operations.

Figure 40 - Floating microplastics (330 µm to 5 mm) detected at the abandoned mussel farm before (March 2023) and after the cleaning operations according to their shapes and colours (sum of the n. of particles found in each replicate for each sample).

As for the particles having a size from 20 μm to 5 mm (Figure 41 and Figure 42), in March 2023, a total of 174 microplastic particles were collected. The concentration, normalised to cubic metres, was 8'700 particles / m^3 . The predominant colour of the microplastics collected was black and the most common shapes were fragments (flat and irregular). In October 2023, a total of 796 microplastic particles were collected, with a concentration of 39'800 particles / m^3 , the highest detected during the monitoring. The predominant microplastics were blue irregular fragments. In March 2024, a total of 242 microplastic particles were detected, and the concentration was 12'100 particles / m^3 . Blue fragments and filaments were the most common microplastic detected during this survey. Lastly, in August 2024, a total of 197 microplastic particles were collected, resulting in 9850 particles / m^3 . The predominant colour of the microplastics collected was "Other Colour" and the shape was filaments.

Figure 41 - Floating microplastics (20 μm - 5 mm) detected at the abandoned mussel farm before (March 2023) and after the cleaning operations.

Figure 42- Floating microplastics (20 µm to 5 mm) detected at the abandoned mussel farm before (march 2023) and after the cleaning operations according to their shapes and colours (sum of the n. of particles found in each replicate for each sample).

5.2.3.2 Microplastic assessment in sediments

Lagoon site: Sacca Fisola

The results related to the microplastics analysed in the sediments collected at Sacca Fisola were shown in

Figure 43 and Figure 44. In November 2022, the average concentration was 332.18 ± 76.41 particles / kg. Blue and black filaments are the most common category recorded. In March 2023, a total of 113 particles were identified. The average concentration of microplastics, calculated on dry weight was 155.38 ± 31.81 particles / kg. The predominant colour of the collected microplastics was black, and the shape was irregular fragments. In October 2023, 72 particles were identified. The average concentration of microplastics was 110.27 ± 38.66 particles / kg. The predominant colour of the collected microplastics was black and the most common shapes were filaments and flat fragments. In March 2024, 49 particles were identified, and the average concentration was 68.52 ± 14.93 particles / kg represented mainly by blue filaments. In August 2024, 79 particles were identified resulting in an average concentration of 155.38 ± 31.81 particles / kg. The predominant colour of the collected microplastics was blue and the most common shape was filaments.

In Figure 45 the results of the granulometry analyses performed in each sample were shown. The different grain sized varied slightly comparing the samples, and the sediments were generally mainly composed by sand, except for those collected in March 2023.

Figure 43 - Microplastics observed in the sediments of Sacca Fisola after the cleaning operations. 43 -

Figure 44 - Microplastics observed in the sediments of Sacca Fisola after the cleaning operations, according to their shapes and colours (sum of the n. of particles found in each replicate for each sample).

Figure 45 - Sediment grain sizes for the various sampling campaigns.

Coastal site: abandoned mussel farm

The results related to the microplastics analysed in the sediments collected at the abandoned mussel farm were shown in Figure 46 and Figure 47. In March 2023, a total of 36 microplastic particles were collected in the sediment at the Abandoned Mussel Farm. The average concentration was 52.46 ± 11.15 particles / kg. The most common

particle type was blue filaments, indicating, as for floating microplastics, a possible origin from degraded plastic or textile materials deriving from fishing nets and ropes. A total of 43 microplastic particles were collected in October 2023. The mean concentration was 61.31 ± 14.41 particles / kg. The predominant colour was “Other Colour (OC)” and the most common shape was film. In March 2024, 48 plastic particles were extracted. The mean concentration was 61.98 ± 22.64 particles / kg, mainly due to the presence of blue filaments. In August 2024, a total of 49 microplastic particles were collected, corresponding to a mean concentration of 70.87 ± 14.25 particles / kg. As observed in the previous campaign, the most common microplastic was represented by blue filaments.

In Figure 48 the results of the granulometry analyses performed in each sample were shown. The different grain sized varied slightly comparing the samples, and the sediments were mainly composed by mud fraction.

Figure 46 - Microplastics observed in the sediments of Sacca Fisola after the cleaning operations.

Figure 47- Microplastics detected in the sediments at the abandoned mussel farm before (march 2023) and after the cleaning operations according to their shapes and colours (sum of the n. of particles found in each replicate for each sample).

Figure 48 – Sediment grain sizes for the various sampling campaigns.

5.2.3.3 Microplastic assessment in biota

The data for microplastics in biota before and after cleaning operations are reported in this Deliverable because the methods and protocols used to assess their presence were not defined properly in the previous Deliverable 2.3.

For bivalves, three different species of filter feeders were sampled according to their presence in the studied areas: *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Magallana gigas* and *Ostreola stentina*.

For fish, microplastics were extracted from the gastrointestinal tract of a wide range of species, both commercial and non-commercial species.

Lagoon site: Sacca Fisola

The data related to biometric measurements and microplastic presence in filter feeder bivalves collected during the pre- and post-cleaning surveys performed at Sacca Fisola were shown in Table 26, Figure 49 (as mean value and S.E.) and Figure 50 (sum of the n. microplastic particles according to shapes and colours).

Table 26 – Analysed bivalve species and biometric parameters detected in the various sampling surveys.

Survey	Species	N.	Length cm	Weight g
February 2022	<i>M. galloprovincialis</i>	20	5.65 ± 0.22	7.26 ± 0.76
November 2022	<i>O. stentina</i>	9	3.94 ± 0.23	2.00 ± 0.29
	<i>M. gigas</i>	10	8.47 ± 1.20	8.68 ± 1.84
March 2023	<i>M. gigas</i>	10	7.59 ± 0.35	9.91 ± 1.93
October 2023	<i>M. gigas</i>	10	6.40 ± 0.41	5.59 ± 1.58
March 2024	<i>M. galloprovincialis</i>	18	4.83 ± 0.69	4.23 ± 0.76
August 2024	<i>M. gigas</i>	10	10.00 ± 0.85	23.15 ± 2.74

In February 2022, the mean concentration of microplastics in mussel soft tissues was 2.27 ± 0.42 particles / g. The predominant colour of the microplastics identified was

blue and the shapes were filaments and irregular fragments. In November 2022, the concentration detected in oysters was 1.65 ± 0.68 particles / g in *O. stentina* and 0.64 ± 0.46 particles / g in *M. gigas*. For both species, the predominant colour was white the shapes were irregular fragments for the former and filaments for the latter. From March 2023 to August 2024, the mean MP concentrations in bivalve surf tissues were quite similar, ranging from 0.49 ± 0.10 particles / g in October 2023 to 0.11 ± 0.02 particles / g in August 2024. Blue filaments were frequently the most common particol type, together with irregular fragments of different colours.

Figure 49 - Microplastics observed in filter feeder bivalves before and after the cleaning operations.

Sacca Fisola

Figure 50 - Microplastics observed in filter feeder bivalves before and after the cleaning operations, according to their shapes and colours (sum of the n. of particles found in each replicate for each sample).

The data related to biometric measurements and microplastic presence in fish collected during the pre- and post-cleaning surveys performed at Sacca Fisola were

shown in Table 27, Figure 51 (as mean value and S.E.) and

Figure 52 (sum of the n. microplastic particles according to shapes and colours).

Table 27 – Analysed fish species and biometric parameters detected in the various sampling surveys.

Survey	Species	N.	Fish Length cm	Fish Weight g	Digestive tract g
February 2022	<i>Atherina boyeri</i> <i>Chelon auratus</i> <i>Chelon labrosus</i> <i>Chelon ramada</i> <i>Gobius paganellus</i> <i>Pomatoschistus marmoratus</i> <i>Solea solea</i> <i>Symphodus roissali</i> <i>Syngnathus typhle</i> <i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	22	12.23 ± 1.22	n.d.	1.06 ± 0.17
March 2023	<i>Atherina boyeri</i> <i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i> <i>Liza ramada</i> <i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i> <i>Solea solea</i>	18	16.65 ± 1.77	71.33 ± 21.33	4.21 ± 0.98

	<i>Pomatoschistus marmoratus</i> <i>Sparus aurata</i>				
October 2023	<i>Atherina boyeri</i> <i>Solea solea</i> <i>Liza ramada</i> <i>Gobius paganellus</i> <i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	9	12.78 ± 1.82	28.00 ± 10.99	1.52 ± 0.40
March 2024	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i> <i>Solea solea</i> <i>Atherina boyeri</i> <i>Sparus aurata</i> <i>Liza ramada</i>	15	21.22 ± 2.57	145.27 ± 32.50	8.72 ± 2.68
August 2024	<i>Liza ramada</i> <i>Boops boops</i> <i>Liza saliens</i> <i>Solea Solea</i> <i>Trachurus trachurus</i> <i>Liza aurata</i>	11	44.11 ± 5.28	16.88 ± 0.89	1.44 ± 0.29

The fish analysed at Sacca Fisola in February 2022 showed the highest microplastic contamination of 8.02 ± 1.39 particles / g. Irregular fragments of various colours and blue filaments were the most common types of particles. From March 2023 to March 2024, microplastic concentrations were quite similar in the analysed fish, with values ranging from 1.31 ± 0.49 particles / g to 0.81 ± 0.27 particles / g. In the last sampling campaign, the values increased, reaching the concentration of 4.34 ± 1.41 particles / g. Most frequent particles were generally irregular fragments of different colours (mainly transparent, blue and black) and blue filaments.

Sacca Fisola

Figure 51 - Microplastics observed in fish at Sacca Fisola before and after the cleaning operations.

Figure 52 - Microplastics observed in fish at Sacca Fisola before and after the cleaning operations, according to their shapes and colours (sum of the n. of particles found in each replicate for each sample).

Coastal site: abandoned mussel farm

The data related to biometric measurements and microplastic presence in *M. galloprovincialis* collected during the pre- and post-cleaning surveys performed at the abandoned mussel farm are shown in Table 28, (as mean value and S.E.) and Figure 54 (sum of the n. microplastic particles according to shapes and colours).

Table 28 – Analysed bivalve species and biometric parameters detected in the various sampling surveys.

Survey	Species	N.	Length cm	Weight g
February 2022	<i>M. galloprovincialis</i>	20	5.79 ± 0.22	6.88 ± 0.75
March 2023	<i>M. galloprovincialis</i>	10	5.88 ± 0.25	5.97 ± 0.74
October 2023	<i>M. galloprovincialis</i>	10	7.19 ± 0.23	8.76 ± 0.54
March 2024	<i>M. galloprovincialis</i>	20	6.50 ± 0.22	5.88 ± 0.55
August 2024	<i>M. galloprovincialis</i>	10	3.62 ± 0.16	1.87 ± 0.21

In February 2022, the average concentration of microplastics detected in the mussel tissues was 1.13 ± 0.17 particles /g. The predominant categories were mostly black and blue and blue filaments. In May 2023, the microplastic mean value was 2.62 ± 0.83 particles / g and almost all particles were blue filaments. In October 2023, the value was 2.30 ± 0.54 particles / g and also in this sample blue filaments prevailed. In March 2024, the concentration was 0.41 ± 0.07 particles / g with a prevalence of blue and transparent irregular fragments. Lastly, in August 2024, the concentration of microplastics detected was 1.48 ± 0.84 particles / g (mostly black fragments and blue filaments).

Figure 53 - Microplastics observed in mussels at the abandoned mussel farm before and after the cleaning operations.

Figure 54 - Microplastics observed in mussels at the abandoned mussel before and after the cleaning operations, according to their shapes and colours (sum of the n. of particles found in each replicate for each sample).

The data related to biometric measurements and microplastic presence in fish collected during the pre- and post-cleaning surveys performed at the abandoned mussel farm were shown in

Survey	Species	N.	Fish Length cm	Fish Weight g	Digestive tract g
February 2022	<i>Merlangius merlangus</i> <i>Solea solea</i> <i>Squalus acanthias</i>	5	71.75 ± 5.22	n.d.	61.93 ± 2.38
March 2023	<i>Umbrina cirrosa</i> <i>Chelidonichthys lucerna</i> <i>Gobius niger</i> <i>Spicara maena</i> <i>Solea solea</i>	7	20.73 ± 2.19	101.65 ± 20.22	5.23 ± 1.91
October 2023	<i>Diplodus sargus</i> <i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	13	23.88 ± 2.27	171.00 ± 28.71	5.27 ± 1.23

	<i>Solea solea</i> <i>Scorpaena porcus</i> <i>Solea solea</i> <i>Mustelus mustelus</i>				
March 2024	<i>Umbrina cirrhosa</i> <i>Trachurus trachurus</i> <i>Solea solea</i>	7	25.89 ± 1.32	162.71 ± 29.80	5.11 ± 1.37
August 2024	<i>Solea solea</i> <i>Sciaena umbra</i> <i>Sarda sarda</i> <i>Chelon auratus</i> <i>Mustelus mustelus</i> <i>Diplodus puntazzo</i>	19	36.30 ± 3.46	n.d.	8,83 ± 2,41

Table 29, Figure 55 (as mean value and S.E.) and Figure 56 (sum of the n. microplastic particles according to shapes and colours).

Table 29 – Analysed fish species and biometric parameters detected in the various sampling surveys.

Survey	Species	N.	Fish Length cm	Fish Weight g	Digestive tract g
February 2022	<i>Merlangius merlangus</i> <i>Solea solea</i> <i>Squalus acanthias</i>	5	71.75 ± 5.22	n.d.	61.93 ± 2.38
March 2023	<i>Umbrina cirrosa</i> <i>Chelidonichthys lucerna</i> <i>Gobius niger</i> <i>Spicara maena</i> <i>Solea solea</i>	7	20.73 ± 2.19	101.65 ± 20.22	5.23 ± 1.91
October 2023	<i>Diplodus sargus</i> <i>Trachurus trachurus</i> <i>Solea solea</i> <i>Scorpaena porcus</i> <i>Solea solea</i> <i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	13	23.88 ± 2.27	171.00 ± 28.71	5.27 ± 1.23
March 2024	<i>Umbrina cirrhosa</i> <i>Trachurus trachurus</i> <i>Solea solea</i>	7	25.89 ± 1.32	162.71 ± 29.80	5.11 ± 1.37
August 2024	<i>Solea solea</i> <i>Sciaena umbra</i> <i>Sarda sarda</i> <i>Chelon auratus</i> <i>Mustelus mustelus</i> <i>Diplodus puntazzo</i>	19	36.30 ± 3.46	n.d.	8,83 ± 2,41

The analyses on the gastrointestinal tracts of fish collected at the abandoned mussel farm showed similar values over time, also comparing the pre- and post cleaning surveys. The concentration of microplastic ranged from 0.88 ± 0.45 particles / g in

March 2023 to 2.19 ± 0.91 in March 2024. In all the analysed samples, blue filaments were the most frequent particles, followed by irregular fragments of different colours.

Abandoned Mussel Farm

Figure 55 - Microplastics observed in fish at the abandoned mussel farm before and after the cleaning operations.

Abandoned Mussel Farm

Figure 56 - Microplastics observed in mussels at the abandoned mussel before and after the cleaning operations, according to their shapes and colours (sum of the n. of particles found in each replicate for each sample).

The assessment of microplastic abundance performed in surface waters, sediments and biota (mussels and fish) highlighted their presence in all samples and matrices but varying in their abundances spatially and over time.

The concentrations of floating microplastics recorded in this study in the Venice coastal area were comparable to those observed in Vianello et al. (2018) in front of the Venice Lagoon, where microplastics generally varied from 0.3 to 1.78 particle/m³. It is well known that local microplastic accumulation patterns depend on the complex interaction between plastic sources (mainly macroplastic items) and the environmental conditions prevailing in the area. The highest concentrations of microplastics in water, sediments and fish were found in the Lagoon site, more influenced by the direct input of plastic items from the city of Venice and characterised by high presence of macrolitter.

It is worth noting that floating microplastics having size from 20 µm to 5 mm showed high concentrations and variability, ranging at Sacca Fisola from 25800 to 1950 particles / m³ and at the abandoned mussel farm from 39800 to 8700 particles / m³, highlighting that the small microplastic are the most abundant in these environments.

Filaments, and in particular blue ones, were abundant in all the environmental matrices analysed, in particular at the abandoned mussel farm. They could originate from the ropes and nets used in fishing and harvesting activities.

6 Case study: Ave River estuary, Portugal

6.1 Ecological assessment in the Ave River estuary

Transitional ecosystems are among the most degraded areas on the planet and those most subjected to the effects of climate change and human pressures. Many human activities affect water quality, including agriculture, industry, urbanisation, disposal of human waste, pollution, mining, and climate change. In 2000, the European Union established its framework for the protection, improvement, and sustainable use of Europe's water resources by launching the Water Framework Directive (WFD, 2000). The WFD was pioneering because its approach integrates both the chemical and ecological states in defining water quality (Vincent, 2002). Although the Directive requires the assessment of hydromorphological, physical and chemical elements, the

assessment of the biological communities is necessary to assess the ecological status, through the analysis of the structure of macroinvertebrate, fish, macrophyte, phytobenthos and phytoplankton communities. The classification scheme (Figure 57) illustrates how the different analysed elements are combined and how the “one-out, all-out” principle is applied to achieve the final water quality classification.

The measurement of the ecological status makes it possible to evaluate the effect of human activity on water ecosystems, being an essential tool for the sustainable management of water resources. The legislation requires the periodic assessment of all water bodies, including rivers, lakes, estuaries, coastal waters and groundwaters. Moreover, the water body typology is essential to select the type-specific approach to the estimation of the water quality. Water types are then assigned to a classification system that grades their deviation from reference state (Figure 58; high, good, moderate, poor and bad), with no, or very minor, disturbance from human activities. The main objective of the WFD is to implement measures to achieve “good ecological status” of every natural water bodies.

Figure 57 – WFD classification scheme of surface water status using “one-out, all-out” principle; H – high status, G – good status, M – moderate status, P – poor status, B – bad status.

Figure 58 – Ecological Quality Ratio (EQR) used to determine the ecological water quality status regarding the biological parameters.

Micro and macro litter represent another issue contributing to the degradation of water bodies, although these parameters are not evaluated in the WFD. However, their impact on the aquatic ecosystems, in particular on the biota and food webs, is not completely understood. Macro litter has become a dilemma for the whole society, affecting all sectors: economic, social, environmental and even cultural, thus increasingly becoming a multigenerational problem. Macro litter is mostly discharged into aquatic ecosystems and transported by currents to diverse areas, also far from their sources. Macro litter is composed of a wide variety of materials from various sources; however, plastics are, by far, the most abundant material recorded (Arthur et al., 2009). Plastic marine debris are exposed to physical, chemical and biological stressors, resulting in smaller fragments, known as microplastics (Gago et al., 2018). The growing input of both macro litter and microplastics is causing a wide spectrum of environmental, economic and social impacts.

Rivers act as pipelines to the ocean, channelling the waste that is dumped into the estuaries. Thus, acquiring data on these ecosystems contribute to a better understanding on the accumulation of litter into the ocean from terrestrial sources. To increase the knowledge on the contamination impacts on wild populations by both anthropogenic macro litter and microplastic, more biomonitoring studies on those areas are still and urgently needed, also to support appropriate management measures. In addition, these field monitoring are being considered crucial in the scope of national and international regulations, such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) of the European Union (Directive 2008/56/EC).

The Ave River hydrological basin has been monitored since 2009 for its ecological status/potential in compliance with the WFD ([Wise – Water Framework Directive - 2nd River Basin Management Plans](#)). This assessment has been made in three monitoring cycles, and the evaluation is represented in Figure 59. The ecological assessment revealed a degradation of the ecosystems at the last part of the Ave River, including

its estuary, reaching the worst classification (Bad) in the last monitoring programme (2022-2027; Figure 4; PGRH, 2022). According to the monitoring programmes, the degradation of the ecological status of the Ave River estuary over time is associated to the increase of anthropogenic pressures, namely: augment of the population, urban environment, tourism, and recreational activities. Moreover, the increase of industrial activities in the entire hydrographic basin (Figure 2) is a factor that influence the quality of water ecosystem. Another factor is the decrease of freshwater fluxes due to climate change (augmenting the residence time of the water masses inside the estuary). This is a common pattern in Portuguese estuaries, however, there is not up-to-date data for Ave River estuary that can corroborate this reduction in the freshwater fluxes.

Figure 59 – Ave River hydrographic basin with the final classification of the ecological status/potential for the three monitoring programmes according to the WFD metrics (source: <https://sniamb.apambiente.pt/>; APA, 2021).

6.2 Methodologies

One transect with three sampling sites was selected to assess the ecological status of Ave estuary. In each site, water and sediments were collected to assess the ecological status of the transitional ecosystems regarding the European current legislation – WFD. The sampling periods for the first evaluation (zero time) were carried out for spring and autumn seasons (spring 2021, autumn 2021, spring 2022, summer

2022, autumn 2022, spring 2023 and autumn 2023) before the implementation of the cleaning technology. After the implementation of the technology, two transects (each one with three sampling sites) were selected one upstream and other downstream the technology implementation region, and the frequency of the campaigns was increased to seasonal (winter 2024, spring 2024, summer 2024, autumn 2024). The marine litter evaluation was also conducted in the same periods to characterize and quantify macro litter and microplastics along five transects, covering the same estuarine area (Figure 60 and Figure 61). After the implementation of the technology, and additional transect was performed over the bubble curtain. Additional campaigns were performed in the same periods to understand the hydrodynamic and morphological characteristics of this estuarine region, their links with the ecological status of the Ave River estuary and the macro litter and microplastics transport (Figure 62).

Figure 60— Sampling campaigns for the ecological status of Ave Estuary.

Figure 61– Sampling campaigns for the macro-litter and microplastics status of Ave Estuary.

Figure 62 – Sampling campaigns for the hydrodynamic and morphological status of Ave Estuary.

6.2.1 *In situ* methodologies

In each of the selected sites, using a boat, physical and chemical water parameters were measured sub-superficially (<0.50 m depth): pH, conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$),

temperature (°C), salinity and dissolved oxygen (mg/L and %) using a multiparameter probe (Multi 3630 IDS SET F). The photic water layer depth was also measured with the Secchi disk. Additionally, water samples were collected and transported to the laboratory at 4 °C under dark conditions for further analyses (e.g. chlorophyll *a*, nutrients, metals).

Macroinvertebrate community samples were collected using a Van Veen grab (≈ 0.051 m² of area). In each site, three drags were performed, and the sediment samples were preserved in formaldehyde 4% with Rose Bengal dye. One additional sediment sample was collected in each site for further analysis: organic matter content and granulometry.

Marine litter (FML) and microplastics (MP) were assessed during the same periods following international guidelines. The evaluation of FML was conducted following standard European guidelines (Hanke et al., 2013, 2023) through visual monitoring, which examined the diversity and relative abundance of debris in the area. Monitoring campaigns were carried out monthly from June 2021 to December 2024. FML was observed using binoculars (Olympus 8-16x40 Zoom DPS I) at three different locations in the estuary: downstream, midstream, and upstream (S1: 41.340117°N, 8.748913°W; S2: 41.345022°N, 8.745227°W; S3: 41.351156°N, 8.741285°W) (Figure 63). On the vertical, the three observation points were located at the same level, all of them at the margin of the estuary and with an averaged distance to the water surface between 2 m and 2.5 m. Although some FML objects could be masked by ripples, produced by wind, or small waves, produced by boats passing by, it is worth to mention that observational campaigns were performed during calm days with high visibility.

Figure 63 - Map of the three observation points (S1 – S3) for FML record in the Ave River estuary. Reference system WGS84.

Although the Bubble Barrier is not specifically designed to collect MP, an assessment of these emerging contaminants was, also, conducted in the estuary. Given that most MP originates from the degradation of larger plastics (secondary MP), this study served as a complement to the FML assessment.

MP particles in the water column were evaluated following standardized protocols (Gago et al., 2018), and surveyed under low tide conditions using a manta net with 200 µm mesh size. To quantify the filtered water volume, a flowmeter (Hydro-Bios 438115) was attached to the manta net. The planktonic trawls were performed seasonally (2021-2024) along five different transects (Figure 64). An additional transect was included over the bubble curtain after the implementation of the technology. Samples were stored in glass bottles, transported to laboratory and cooled for further laboratory analysis.

Figure 64 - Map of the five selected transects (T1 – T5) for MP in the Ave River estuary. Reference system WGS84. The additional transect, included after the BB implementation is also indicated).

As already described in MAELSTROM Deliverable 2.2, physical parameters were measured to understand the hydrodynamic behaviour of the Ave River estuary. The field studies included a bathymetric survey, short-term (12.5 hours) and long-term (several weeks) campaigns. Both the short-term and long-term campaigns were performed during summer and winter conditions, meaning respectively a low and high river discharge.

The short-term campaigns were carried out from a boat during spring tide. Flow velocity was measured using an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP, Nortek AquaPro 600 kHz). The ADCP measured velocity with respect to the boat every 1 s in layers of 1 m, sailing from west to east over the transect indicated in Figure 65. The boat was sailing at low speed (1-2 m/s) to get the highest possible accuracy. Accounting for the boat speed, as measured by a GPS on the boat, we obtained the flow velocity in northern and eastern direction. We present width averaged flow velocity for each of the transects during the 13 hours periods of both short-term campaigns. In total 12-13 transects were sailed during the measurement period of

about 12 hours. Additionally, in that 12 hours period also salinity and temperature vertical profiles were measured at 2 fixed locations near the transect, using a multiparametric probe (YSI multiparameter Water Quality Sonde 6920 V2). The probe was lowered at a constant low speed and the measurements of the down cast were selected to obtain profiles of salinity and temperature. Since the results are similar for the two fixed locations, only the results of the fixed locations, where the water depth was largest were considered.

For the long-term campaigns, instruments were deployed for several weeks at two sampling points. At sampling point 1 two CTDs were installed: one close to the bottom and another one floating on a buoy at a constant distance to the surface. Additionally, the Nortek ADCP was mounted upward looking in a frame and lowered to the bed. At sampling point 2, only the CTDs, one CTD at the surface and another one close to the bottom, were installed. All the equipments were measuring at a time interval of 5 minutes. The observations were smoothed using a moving average with a window of 45 minutes for water level and 2 hours for salinity and temperature.

Additionally, current velocity and direction next to the catchment system at the surface and at 1 m depth (Valeport 801 Electromagnetic Current Meter) and vertical profiles of salinity and temperature (YSI multiparameter Water Quality Sonde 6920 V2) in the middle of each one of the designed microplastic transects were measured during each ecological assessment campaigns to assure the stratification of the estuary during the performed campaigns.

Figure 65 - Scheme of the hydrodynamic campaigns performed in the Ave River estuary.

6.2.2 Laboratory procedures

In the laboratory, nutrient quantification (Nitrites (NO₂-), nitrates (NO₃-), ammonia (NH₃ + NH₄⁺) and phosphates (PO₄³⁻) was obtained using a Skalar SAN+ Segmented Flow Analyzer using the following Skalar methods: M461-318 (EPA 353.2), M155-008R (EPA 350.1), and M503-555R (Standard Method 450-P I). For metals analysis (mercury (Hg), lead (Pb), copper (Cu), cadmium (Cd) and nickel (Ni)), the methods used were the Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometry and the Electrothermal Atomic Absorption.

Chlorophyll *a* concentration was determined according to Lorenzen (1967) methodology, and the phytoplankton biomass was calculated after spectrophotometer readings.

The content of organic matter in the sediments was measured in each sediment samples. Each sample was put on an oven (60°C) to dry until constant weight (≈1 week) (dry weight). After this procedure, the sediment samples were burned overnight in a muffle furnace at 450°C and, after cooling, they were weighted (muffle weight). The content or organic matter was determined according to the equation:

$$\text{Organic matter (\%)} = \frac{\text{dry weight} - \text{muffle weight}}{\text{dry weight}} \times 100$$

The sediment samples, after burned in the muffle, were processed to determinate their granulometry. The samples were shacked through a tower of sieves with different size mesh (250µm, 100µm and 50µm) that allowed to differentiate the sediment grain sizes present in each sample. Each fraction retained in each sieve was used to differentiate the samples and determined the type of sediment by comparing with the Udden-Wentworth scale (Wentworth, 1922).

Macroinvertebrates samples were screened with tweezers and the organisms were conserved in ethanol 96%. The identification procedure was conducted in a binocular stereoscope and all organisms were identified up to the species level, whenever possible, using the specific dichotomous identification key of Hayward and Ryland (2017).

Univariate descriptors were calculated:

- abundance, N
- species richness, S
- Margalef index (Margalef, 1958), the index has been introduced to make richness independent of the sample size.

$$d = \frac{(S - 1)}{\ln(N)}$$

- Shannon index,

$$H' = -\sum p_i \log_2 p_i$$

- $H' = -\sum p_i \log_2 p_i$ ($p_i = n_i/N$, with n_i being the i -th taxon abundance; Shannon & Weaver, 1949).

It expresses the "uncertainty" in predicting which species a randomly selected individual belongs to, with values ranging between 0 and ∞ . Like the other diversity indices, it takes into account the richness and distribution of abundances among taxa. A high sample size is assumed ($N \rightarrow \infty$).

- Pielou evenness (Pielou, 1966). It quantifies the evenness in the distribution of abundances between taxa, with values ranging between 0 and 1.

$$J' = \frac{H'}{\log_2(S)}$$

- AMBI biotic index (Borja et al., 2000). Biotic indices are based on the paradigm that the taxonomic composition is affected by the quality of the system, in terms of the quantitative ratio (abundances) between sensitive and tolerant species. However, biotic indices have been also applied to other types of impacts. Calculation steps are the following: 1) taxa are attributed to one of five "ecological groups" describing the taxon sensitivity, based on lists of species (December 2020 version, <https://ambi.azti.es/>; if the taxon is missing, a class has been assigned, when possible, based on expert opinion); 2) a biotic coefficient ranging between 1 and 6 is calculated according to the formula:

$$BC = (0 \times \%GI) + (1.5 \times \%GII) + (3 \times \%GIII) + (4.5 \times \%GIV) + (6 \times \%GV)$$

GI-GV are the percentage abundances of the five ecological groups; 7 is given in case of ozoic samples; 3) a discrete biotic index BI 1-7 may be attributed according to reference BC intervals; however, it has not been applied in the present analysis.

- M-AMBI multimetric index (Bald et al., 2005; Muxika et al., 2007). The index integrates S , H' and AMBI through complex multivariate calculations, however it has been demonstrated that it approximates the simple mean of normalised metrics (Sigovini et al. 2013), with 0-1 normalisation calculated over the following range: a minimum value corresponding to theoretical conditions ($S = 0$, $H' = 0$, AMBI = 6) and a maximum value corresponding either to given high-quality reference conditions (which generally differ according to the monitored environment) or to the highest values in the dataset (the lowest in the case of

AMBI), the latter being applied in the present analysis (calculated from the whole dataset of marine and lagoon community data). The M-AMBI index therefore assumes values between 0 and 1 (or slightly higher than 1).

- BAT index, integrates, in a cumulative index, three widely used metrics – Shannon–Wiener index (H0), Margalef index (d) and AMBI – which are based on different approaches when evaluating system status

Water samples for microplastics characterization were digested (10% potassium hydroxide solution), filtered (GF/C 1.2 μm /pore and $\text{\O}=47$ mm) and dried (40°C, 48h) according to standardized procedures (Frias et al., 2019, 2022). Several filter blanks were used to evaluate contamination. Each particle was carefully observed in a stereomicroscope with dedicated camera and high-definition pictures were taken. Each particle was identified, digitally measured and sorted by type (fragment, pellet, fiber, film) and colour.

Normality and homogeneity of variance were verified for the obtained data. A two-way ANOVA was performed to compare microplastics size, type and colour among distinct sampling transects and seasons. All the statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics Version 27 (IBM®).

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Ave River estuary hydromorphology

The estuary of the Ave River is a small shallow water estuary of 2 km length and between 90 and 120 m-wide, limited by a weir constructed for an historical water mill that prevent the oceanic water going upstream. The bathymetric configuration (Figure 66) revealed a shallow water estuary with mean depths of 4 m (referred to the MSL – Mean Sea Level). The deepest regions, of around 8 m (referred to the MSL), can be found in the upstream estuarine region.

Figure 66 – Bathymetry of the Ave Estuary and adjacent coastal region in m (referred to the MSL). Data was acquired in September 2021 in a dedicated campaign under the scope of the MAELSTROM project.

The river flow on the Ave River estuary is low, with an average value of $30 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, maximum values around $60 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and minimum values next to zero (Figure 67a), reflecting the annual precipitation cycle with strong estuarine flows in winter and weaker flows in summer. Extreme river flows can reach $450 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, however, those events are rare (Figure 67b). Notice that the data available only covers a period between 1978 and 2000. Current trends associated, for example, with climate change conditions or with changes in the water use, are not contemplated in this database.

Figure 67 – Ave estuary river flow: a) Monthly mean river flow and maximum and minimum river flow measured for each month; b) Measured river flow. Data was extracted from SNIRH (<https://snirh.apambiente.pt/>) for the last hydrographic basin station available in the water course, and between 1978 and 2000.

To complement the dataset and feed the hydrodynamic numerical model already described in MAELSTROM Deliverable 2.2, a hydrological numerical model was implemented for the Ave River hydrographic basin. The results are shown in Figure 68.

Figure 68 - Modelled discharge (m^3/s) at the estuary of the Ave River.

The low river flow found in this estuarine region is a clear indicator that the oceanic conditions will be the main drivers of its dynamic. Waves and tides are highly energetic in this area. The waves come mainly from the north-west and west directions, with a mean significant height of 2 m and peak period between 9 s and 13 s. During storminess periods, extremely high energetic conditions are produced on the continental shelf, with normal significant heights between 3 m and 6 m that can reach 9 m or 12 m (Viitak et al, 2021). However, due to the morphological configuration of the estuary and its breakwaters, it is protected from the waves coming from the ocean. So, the main driver of this estuary is the tide, which, in the NW-Portuguese

coast, is mesotidal with a semi-diurnal regime with a 12.4 h-long period (Iglesias et al., 2019). This makes the estuary poorly mixed, presenting strong stratification during mostly part of the year, as clearly demonstrated in the hydrodynamic campaigns performed in the Ave River estuary and detailed described in MAELSTROM deliverable 2.2.

Both short-term campaigns were carried out during lower-than-average river discharge (9 and 18 m³/s, respectively), and a strong vertical stratification was depicted. The width averaged flow velocity was also low, didn't exceeding a magnitude of 0.5 m/s for the 1 m depth intervals for both campaigns (Figure 69 and Figure 70).

Figure 69 - Width averaged flow velocity to the north (top; m/s), salinity (middle; psu) and temperature (bottom; °C) for the 'summer' short-term campaign. The blue lines are the estimated water level and black diamonds and lines denote the (lowest in the transect) bed level.

Figure 70 - Width averaged flow velocity to the north (top; m/s), salinity (middle; psu) and temperature (bottom; °C) for the winter short-term campaign. The blue lines are the estimated water level and black diamonds and lines denote the (lowest in the transect) bed level.

Long-term campaigns results revealed lower velocities of the water masses except during high river flow conditions, where the velocity can reach 0.63 m/s and the water column is entirely filled by freshwater (and Figure 72). Tidal cycles can be seen in the current and salinity plots when low river flow conditions are presented. Generally, the along-channel flow was towards the ocean (ebb flow). However, this oceanward direction is more marked in the surface layers where the effect of the river flow is more noticeable. Near the surface, the flow was always seawards, which can be the result of the constant input of freshwater at the weir in combination with the estuarine

circulation. In the bottom layers the flow reversed to an upstream direction for short periods within a day, corresponding to the flood tide. This revealed the existence of two well separated layers. In addition, during low river flow conditions, lower in the water column the estuary was nearly as salt as the ocean, whereas near the surface it varied much within a tidal cycle, demonstrating also the strong stratification of this system. Temperature values revealed the seasonal variation of riverine and oceanic waters.

Figure 71 - Time series of modelled Ave River flow (a) and observed water depth (b), temperature (c), salinity (d) and along-channel velocity component measured at point 1 B (e) during the winter long-term campaign. 1 and 2 refer to the observation site. S and B refer to the near-surface and near-bottom sensor, respectively. Positive values (red) indicated an upstream direction of the velocity.

Figure 72 - Time series of modelled Ave River flow (a) and observed water depth (b), temperature (c), salinity (d) and along-channel velocity component measured at point 1 B (e) during the summer long-term campaign. 1 and 2 refer to the observation site. S and B refer to the near-surface and near-bottom sensor, respectively. Positive values (red) indicated an upstream direction of the velocity.

Stratification was also depicted in the results obtained from the vertical profiles measured during the ecological campaigns. Stratification was observed in almost all the campaigns except on the 29/02/2024, where the water column was entirely fresh probably associated with a high river flow. The salinity profiles during stratification go from next to 0 at the surface to around 35 at the bottom. An exception are the

profiles measured on the 13/09/2024 where the salinity at the surface was next to 20, probably associated with a low river flow. Profiles do not differ substantially from downstream (P1) to upstream (P5) locations. The temperature demonstrates again the seasonal variation for the freshwater and oceanic water.

Figure 73 - Vertical profiles of salinity and temperature measured during the ecological assessment campaigns at the centre of each one of the microplastic transects.

The strong stratification and the low velocities observed in this estuarine region are indicators of high residence times, which can produce retention of pollutants, microplastics and marine litter inside the estuary during long times, damaging the ecosystem. However, this more common behaviour can change with punctual high-flow conditions.

6.3.2 Physical, chemical and hydromorphological characterization

Table 30 shows the characterization of the physical and chemical, and hydromorphological elements measured in each sampling campaign along the project period (spring21 to autumn23 stand for the period before BB installation and winter24 to autumn24 for the period after BB installation). The Ave River estuary showed low oxygen values for transitional water (A1.1 north strait channel type). High content of nutrients in water column were recorded along the full sampling period with similar values before and after BB installation. High contents of organic matter were also recorded. Sediments are characterized by coarse silt to very fine sand (namely after BB installation), and the structure of the margins are distinct (right margin artificial, and the left margin is a wetland). Constant freshwater flow from upstream, increased in rainy periods, is a natural freshwater flow observed in the last section of the Ave River estuary, without exposure to waves resulting from the shape of the estuary inlet (Figure 67, Figure 68, Figure 69 and Table 30).

Table 30 – Results of physical and chemical elements, as well as hydromorphological parameters measured along the project period.

Sampling Periods	PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL ELEMENTS				HYDROMORPHOLOGICAL ELEMENTS				
	O2 (%)	Nitrate+Nitrites (mg N/L)	Ammonia (mgN/L)	Phosphate (mg P/L)	Organic Matter (%)	Granulometry	Intertidal Zone Structure	Freshwater flow	Exposure to waves
Reference values	109	1.00	0.30	0.11					
Spring21	95.07 ± 1.39	1.41 ± 0.60	0.06 ± 0.006	0.21 ± 0.04	12.03 ± 4.21	Coarse silt/Medium sand			
Autumn21	94.37 ± 1.25	1.34 ± 0.22	1.19 ± 0.43	0.42 ± 0.06	9.030 ± 5.66	Coarse silt/Medium sand			
Spring22	92.67 ± 1.25	1.57 ± 0.07	0.92 ± 0.09	0.15 ± 0.02	9.840 ± 6.60	Coarse silt/Medium sand			
Summer22	95.08 ± 1.96				21.04 ± 9.36	Very fine sand			
Autumn22	96.70 ± 0.49	0.47 ± 0.01	0.48 ± 0.06	0.19 ± 0.006	22.85 ± 11.3	Fine sand			
Spring23	87.93 ± 1.28	1.15 ± 0.11	2.75 ± 0.54	0.77 ± 0.19	19.36 ± 6.86	Fine sand			
Autumn23	95.17 ± 0.73	1.12 ± 0.003	0.28 ± 0.02	0.36 ± 0.003	25.15 ± 6.03	Very fine sand			
Bubble Barrier Installation									
UBB_Winter24(1)	98.07 ± 0.39	0.45 ± 0.0006	0.44 ± 0.05	0.25 ± 0.004	10.48 ± 11.9	Very coarse sand	Right margin = artificial - wall	Constant freshwater flow from upstream, with increase in rainy periods	Null
DBB_Winter24(1)	97.57 ± 0.40	0.45 ± 0.0006	0.46 ± 0.02	0.25 ± 0.00	24.50 ± 3.16	Very fine sand			
UBB_Winter24(2)	99.70 ± 0.42	0.45 ± 0.001	0.38 ± 0.03	0.24 ± 0.002	10.48 ± 10.2	Very coarse sand	Left margin = artificial - wetland		
DBB_Winter24(2)	99.17 ± 0.45	0.45 ± 0.001	0.38 ± 0.03	0.24 ± 0.001	20.08 ± 1.83	Fine sand			
UBB_Spring24	95.53 ± 0.48	1.83 ± 0.08	0.39 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.26	20.09 ± 8.52	Fine sand			
DBB_Spring24	94.00 ± 0.16	1.92 ± 0.06	0.41 ± 0.06	1.58 ± 0.12	25.89 ± 6.45	Very fine sand			
UBB_Summer24	83.03 ± 1.90	0.98 ± 0.10	0.39 ± 0.17	0.71 ± 0.28	17.43 ± 8.29	Very fine sand			
DBB_Summer24	82.43 ± 0.17	0.96 ± 0.07	0.39 ± 0.14	0.70 ± 0.27	20.08 ± 5.33	Very fine sand			
UBB_Autumn24	89.57 ± 3.19	1.49 ± 0.03	1.32 ± 0.02	1.40 ± 0.02	26.93 ± 2.97	Very fine sand			
DBB_Autumn24	87.97 ± 0.42	1.54 ± 0.03	1.35 ± 0.03	1.39 ± 0.11	28.89 ± 4.48	Very fine sand			

6.3.3 Biological elements

The results of the two biological elements analysed are presented in Table 31. Overall, the macroinvertebrates communities showed a low abundance, richness, and diversity values. Indeed, these low values resulting in high AMBI values (high ecosystem disturbance) and low BAT values that reflects low boundary values (> 0.79 = excellent; $[0.78-0.53[$ = good; $[0.52-0.44[$ = moderate status; APA, 2021) and poor ecosystem status classification for this aquatic ecosystem (Table XX). Regarding the phytoplankton evaluation, low chlorophyll a concentration was observed for all sites and sampling periods. This allowed to have a reliable assessment of the Ave Estuary as a good ecological status regarding only the phytoplankton element (Ecological Quality Ratio = 90% percentile reference value (6.67)/90% percentile of the samples). The boundary values for the EQR result for Chlorophyll *a* are > 0.670 = excellent; $[0.47-0.67[$ = good; $[0.30-0.47[$ = moderate status; $[0.20-0.3[$ = bad; < 0.2 poor status (APA, 2021). However, the values obtained so far revealed a bad ecological status considering the macroinvertebrates, in agreement with the ecological status achieved in the 3^o cycle of monitoring program – bad (2021-2027) (Table 32). The biological elements evaluated showed some variation in classification during the study period, particularly within the benthic macroinvertebrate community. However, the ecological quality status of the Ave estuary never achieved a "good" ecological status during the study period. Following the installation of the BB, the ecological assessment results remained unchanged up to the present (approximately 10 months post-installation), with no significant changes observed in any of the evaluated indicators.

Table 31- Biological parameters results (benthic macroinvertebrates and phytoplankton) measured in the transects sampled along the project period.

Sampling Periods	BIOLOGICAL ELEMENTS						
	Abundance	Richness (S)	Margalef (d)	Shannon-Wiener (H')	AMBI	BAT	Chlorophyll <i>a</i> (µg/L)
Reference values			1.9	2.30	2.50		6.67
Spring21	47	2	0.26	0.24	6.00	0.147	4.48 ± 0.83
Autumn21	198	5	0.57	0.79	3.47	0.448	4.64 ± 0.91
Spring22	242	8	1.28	0.98	5.76	0.470	1.47 ± 0.18
Summer22	138	5	0.81	0.29	5.85	0.264	
Autumn22	431	5	0.66	0.23	5.86	0.226	1.28 ± 0.22
Spring23	152	5	0.80	0.16	5.92	0.236	0.79 ± 0.17
Autumn23	141	9	1.62	1.42	4.23	0.698	0.86 ± 0.07
Bubble Barrier Installation							
UBB_Winter24(1)	177	4	0.67	0.63	3.39	0.445	0.09 ± 0.04
DBB_Winter24(1)	2	2	1.44	0.69	1.50	0.707	0.07 ± 0.07
UBB_Winter24(2)	52	4	0.76	0.94	5.02	0.414	0.55 ± 0.26
DBB_Winter24(2)	7	4	1.54	1.28	3.50	0.704	0.39 ± 0.13
UBB_Spring24	37	3	0.55	0.46	5.35	0.277	0.46 ± 0.06
DBB_Spring24	115	1	0.00	0.00	6.00	0.060	0.54 ± 0.08
UBB_Summer24	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	3.75 ± 0.05
DBB_Summer24	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	3.45 ± 0.40
UBB_Autumn24	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	0.51 ± 0.36
DBB_Autumn24	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	ongoing	0.34 ± 0.04

Table 32 - Summary table of the evaluated elements used to assess water quality based on WFD metrics throughout the Maelstrom project, including pre- and post-BB installation phases

SAMPLING PERIODS	ECOLOGICAL STATUS (1)					CHEMICAL STATUS (2)		OVERALL STATUS (1) + (2)
	Physical and Chemical Elements	Specific Pollutants (Cu)	Biological elements		ECOLOGICAL STATUS	Priority Substances (Cd, Pb, Ni, Hg)		
			Chlorophyll <i>a</i> P90	BAT				
Spring21	Moderate	*	Excellent	Poor	Poor	Good	Poor	
Autumn21	Moderate	*	Excellent	Moderate	Moderate	Good	Moderate	
Spring22	Moderate	*	Excellent	Moderate	Moderate	Failing to achieve good	Moderate	
Summer22	Moderate	*	Excellent	Poor	Poor	Good	Poor	
Autumn22	Moderate	*	Excellent	Poor	Poor	Good	Poor	
Spring23	Moderate	*	Excellent	Poor	Poor	Failing to achieve good	Poor	
Autumn23	Moderate	*	Excellent	Good	Moderate	Failing to achieve good	Moderate	
UBB_Winter24(1)	Moderate	*	Excellent	Moderate	Moderate	Failing to achieve good	Moderate	
DBB_Winter24(1)	Moderate	*	Excellent	Good	Moderate	Failing to achieve good	Moderate	
UBB_Winter24(2)	Moderate	*	Excellent	Bad	Bad	Failing to achieve good	Bad	
DBB_Winter24(2)	Moderate	*	Excellent	Good	Moderate	Failing to achieve good	Moderate	
UBB_Spring24	Moderate	*	Excellent	Bad	Bad	Failing to achieve good	Bad	
DBB_Spring24	Moderate	*	Excellent	Poor	Poor	Failing to achieve good	Poor	
UBB_Summer24	Moderate	*	Excellent	Ongoing	Ongoing	Failing to achieve good	Ongoing	
DBB_Summer24	Moderate	*	Excellent	Ongoing	Ongoing	Failing to achieve good	Ongoing	
UBB_Autumn24	Moderate	*	Excellent	Ongoing	Ongoing	Failing to achieve good	Ongoing	
DBB_Autumn24	Moderate	*	Excellent	Ongoing	Ongoing	Failing to achieve good	Ongoing	

6.3.4 Macro litter and microplastics

Macro litter

Significant differences ($p < 0.05$; ANOVA) were observed between seasons, sites, and their interaction (seasons*sites). The data revealed that FML values were highest during winter, spring, and autumn, while the lowest values were recorded in summer (Figure 74). These patterns highlight the combined influence of both temporal (seasonal) and spatial (site-specific) factors on FML dynamics. The highest FML rates coincided with periods of increased precipitation and river discharge. Most FML monitoring campaigns were conducted under conditions of low to average Ave River discharge, with the exception of winter 2022 and autumn and winter 2023.

Figure 74 - Seasonal mean of the three FML observation sites (S1-S3) (\pm standard errors) in items per hour recorded monthly between 2021 and 2024, before and after the Bubble Barrier (BB) installation. Bars with different letters are significantly different between them ($p < 0.05$).

Before the implementation of the Bubble Barrier, significantly higher values ($p < 0.05$) of floating macro-litter (FML) were observed near the mouth of the estuary (S1 - 42.5 ± 6.3 items/h) compared to other sites (S2 - 22.4 ± 2.1 items/h; S3 - 11.7 ± 2.3 items/h; see Figure 76). These findings underscore the significant influence of the urban center on FML accumulation within the estuary, as evidenced by the clear increasing gradient from S3 to S1. This pattern suggests that anthropogenic activities, particularly in densely populated coastal cities, contribute substantially to the

discharge of macro-litter into the water system. Urban areas generate large amounts of waste due to high population density, commercial activities, and tourism, which can lead to increased litter input into the environment. Insufficient waste management infrastructure, illegal dumping, and stormwater runoff further exacerbates the issue by transporting plastic and other debris from city streets, public spaces, and industrial zones into nearby water bodies (Willis et al., 2017)

Moreover, the proximity of S1 to the estuary mouth makes it a natural accumulation zone for floating litter carried downstream by river currents and tidal influences. Coastal cities often act as major sources of marine pollution due to their location at the interface between land and sea. Rainfall events and urban drainage systems play a crucial role in this process, as they facilitate the transfer of litter from land-based sources to aquatic environments (Gacutan et al., 2024). Additionally, recreational activities, fishing, and port operations may further contribute to litter accumulation in these areas (Willis et al., 2017, Gacutan et al., 2024).

After the Bubble Barrier was installed and began operation, a significant reduction in FML ($p < 0.05$) was observed downstream of the technology installation area (S1 - 25.5 ± 5.9 items/h; see Figure 75). No significant differences in FML were noted in S2 (27.6 ± 5.3 items/h) and S3 (12.1 ± 4.7 items/h) after the Bubble Barrier's operation.

Overall, the implementation of the Bubble Barrier resulted in an approximate 40% reduction in FML near the mouth of the Ave estuary. These findings highlight the effectiveness of the Bubble Barrier in reducing FML transport to the downstream areas of the estuary and to the Atlantic Ocean.

Figure 75 - Comparison of the FML items (mean \pm standard errors) per hour recorded monthly, before and after) the Bubble Barrier (BB) implementation, in the three observation sites (S1-S3). The data illustrate temporal variations in FML accumulation and the impact of the BB system on litter retention and reduction. Bars with different letters are significantly different between them (before and after BB) ($p < 0.05$).

In terms of FML composition, despite significant ($p < 0.05$) variability across different months and seasons, artificial polymer materials (plastics) consistently dominated, accounting for more than 85.5% of the total recorded items. Smoking-related waste, including cigarette butts and packaging, constituted 7.3%, while paper and cardboard items made up 6.4%. Metal objects were the least represented category, contributing less than 1% of the total floating litter observed.

Focusing on visual monitoring campaigns conducted at the estuary mouth (S1), located downstream of the Bubble Barrier (BB), the most frequently recorded FML items before the system's implementation were non-foamed plastic fragments (39.3%), foamed plastic fragments (30.1%), plastic bags (12.4%), cigarette butts (9.2%), and paper fragments (9.0%).

Following the installation of the aquatic litter removal technology, the composition of the most common FML items shifted. The top five items remained the same, represented, by the same order, 54.7%, 13.1%, 4.1%, 19.8% and 8.3%, respectively.

Figure 76 - Classification of the Top 5 materials found in the FML assessment in the estuarine mouth (S1) before and after the BB implementation.

Seasonal variations and local human activities, such as tourism and recreational pursuits, likely play a significant role in influencing the amount and composition of litter in this area.

Overall, the findings indicate that the Bubble Barrier is already making a significant impact in reducing FML, effectively intercepting most of these materials before they reach the Atlantic Ocean. By preventing the further dispersal of macro-litter, this technology contributes not only to the preservation of aquatic ecosystems but also to improved environmental quality and human health.

Microplastics

Significant differences in the concentration of identified microplastics (MP) were observed between seasons, sites, and their interaction ($p < 0.05$; ANOVA). Across all sampling locations, more than 25 MP/m³ were recorded in the Ave River estuary, with the highest concentrations detected at upstream transects (Figure 76). Fibers and plastic fragments dominated the composition of MP, collectively accounting for over 87% of the identified particles (Figure 78).

Figure 76 - Seasonal mean concentration of microplastics (MP/m³) collected between 2021 and 2024 (mean \pm standard errors) across the five sampled transects, before and after the installation of the Bubble Barrier (BB). Statistically significant differences between sampling periods are indicated by bars with different letters ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 77 - Examples of identified microplastics in the Aver River estuary: a) Fibers; b) Fragments; c) Films; d) Pellets.

Figure 78 – Percentage distribution of the most common microplastics (MP) collected in the Ave Estuary during sampling campaigns conducted as part of the MAELSTROM project. Data represent aggregated observations from seasonal collections between 2021 and 2024.

Figure 79 – Mean number of microplastics per m³, according to their type, collected between 2021 and 2024.

Fibres (61%) and fragments (26%) together constituted over 87% of the identified microplastics (MP) (see Figure 80). ANOVA results ($p < 0.05$) indicate a significant seasonal and spatial interaction, emphasizing that MP concentrations are strongly influenced by both factors.

Fragments are abundant in marine environments due to the degradation of larger plastic items through physical, chemical, and biological processes. Plastics, especially single-use items like packaging and consumer products, degrade into smaller fragments over time under the influence of UV radiation, wave action, and mechanical abrasion (Thompson et al., 2009). Unlike organic materials, plastics resist biodegradation and instead fragment into micro-sized particles, persisting in the environment for decades (Andrady et al., 2011).

The widespread production and improper disposal of plastic materials exacerbate their presence in marine ecosystems. For example, over 0.19 million tons of synthetic textile fibers alone are released into the ocean annually (Henry et al., 2019), contributing to plastic fragment accumulation. Additionally, marine activities such as fishing and shipping lead to the loss of plastic items, which fragment through wear

and exposure to ocean conditions (Hernandez et al., 2017). Furthermore, biofouling—where marine organisms colonize plastic surfaces—can weaken materials, making them more prone to fragmentation (Andrady et al., 2011). The cumulative impact of these processes results in the significant abundance of plastic fragments in the marine environment, representing a persistent and pervasive pollutant.

Figure 80 – Mean number of microplastics per m³, according to their size class, collected between 2021 and 2024.

The most commonly identified microplastic (MP) particles were between 0.5-1 mm (37%), followed by 0.1-0.5 mm (31%) and 1-2.5 mm (25%), with their distribution being highly influenced by both seasonal and spatial factors (ANOVA, $p < 0.05$).

The prevalence of microplastics in the 0.100-1000 μm range is particularly concerning, as these particles are bioavailable to a wide range of organisms through active or passive ingestion. This size range overlaps with the size of prey consumed by organisms such as zooplankton and ichthyoplankton, which could lead to transfer up the food chain to higher trophic levels, including seafood. These findings emphasize the urgent need for more comprehensive temporal and spatial monitoring of MP pollution in estuaries and other coastal ecosystems.

Following the installation of the Bubble Barrier, an additional microplastic (MP) collection transect was conducted seasonally over the bubble curtain, using the same methodology and manta net as described previously. The average MP concentration in this area was estimated at 81 MP/m³, significantly higher than in other transects.

This finding highlights the effectiveness of the Bubble Barrier in trapping and concentrating microplastics at the water surface, reinforcing its role in mitigating plastic pollution (Figure 81 and Figure 82).

Figure 81 - Comparison of microplastic (MP) concentrations (mean \pm standard error) collected before and after the implementation of the Bubble Barrier (BB). Bars labeled with different letters indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in MP concentrations between pre- and post-installation periods. "BB" represents the transect conducted over the bubble curtain.

Figure 82 - MP sample collected in the bubble curtain with the manta net.

6.3.5 Conclusions

Regarding the results obtained for the ecological assessment of the Ave River estuary, this water body can be classified as moderate to poor according to the assessment of nutrients and the biological element benthic macroinvertebrates, respectively. The analysis of the hydro-morphodynamic conditions revealed a shallow depth high stratified estuary, mainly driven by the tide due to the low river flows and presenting low current velocities.

The FML observations made during before and after BB implementation, showed a significant reduction in FML quantities after passing through the technology. However, to gain a deeper understanding of its performance across various environmental scenarios, additional assessments are needed. These will be essential for ensuring a thorough evaluation of the system's overall effectiveness.

This scientific knowledge is essential for adequate public engagement and political commitment, working together on more effective management of litter and marine and coastal ecosystems. The here-obtained results showed the urgent necessity to developed restoration measures to meet the WFD objectives, where all aquatic ecosystems achieve good ecological status.

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ANNEXES

Table 1- List of taxa identified at the Lagoon site.

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	TAXON	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	<i>Capitella capitata</i>	(Fabricius 1780)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	<i>Capitella minima</i>	Langerhans 1880					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	Capitellidae sp. indet.	Grube 1862					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	<i>Heteromastus filiformis</i>	(Claparède 1864)	X	X			X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	<i>Pseudoleiocapitella fauveli</i>	Harmelin 1864		X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Maldanidae	<i>Euclymene lombricoides</i>	(Quatrefages 1866)	X	X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Maldanidae	Maldanidae sp. 1	Malmgren 1867		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Aphelochaeta sp. indet.</i>	Blake 1991	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Cauleriella bioculata</i>	(Keferstein 1862)	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Chaetozone gibber</i>	Woodham & Chambers 1994	X	X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Chaetozone zetlandica</i>	McIntosh 1911				X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	Cirratulidae sp.	Ryckholt 1851	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Cirriformia tentaculata</i>	(Montagu 1808)		X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Dodecaceria concharum</i>	Örsted 1843		X		X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Dorvilleidae	<i>Schistomeringos rudolphi</i>	(Delle Chiaje 1828)	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Eunice vittata</i>	(Delle Chiaje 1828)	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Lysidice ninetta</i>	Audouin & H Milne Edwards 1833			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Lysidice unicornis</i>	(Grube 1840)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Marphysa sanguinea</i>	(Montagu 1813)	X	X	X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Lumbrineridae	<i>Hilbigneris gracilis</i>	(Ehlers 1868)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Oeonidae	<i>Arabella iricolor</i>	(Montagu 1804)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Onuphidae	<i>Diopatra neapolitana</i>	Delle Chiaje 1841		X	X		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Magelonida	Magelonidae	<i>Magelona filiformis</i>	Wilson 1959					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Opheliida	Opheliidae	<i>Armandia cirrhosa</i>	Filippi 1861	X	X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Orbiniida	Paraonidae	Aricidea (Acmira) sp.	Hartley 1981			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Orbiniida	Paraonidae	<i>Levinsonia gracilis</i>	(Tauber 1879)					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Orbiniida	Paraonidae	<i>Paradoneis lyra</i>	(Southern 1914)	X	X	X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Oweniida	Oweniidae	<i>Galathowenia oculata</i>	(Zachs 1923)	X				X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Glyceridae	<i>Glycera tridactyla</i>	Schmarda 1861	X				

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	TAXON	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nephtyidae	<i>Nephtys hombergii</i>	Savigny in Lamarck 1818	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nereididae	Nereididae sp.	Blainville 1818					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nereididae	<i>Nereis sp. 1</i>	Linnaeus 1758		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nereididae	<i>Perinereis cultrifera</i>	(Grube 1840)				X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Phyllodocidae	<i>Mysta picta</i>	(Quatrefages 1866)	X	X		X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Phyllodocidae	<i>Phyllodoce lineata</i>	(Claparède 1870)	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Phyllodocidae	<i>Phyllodoce sp.</i>	Lamarck 1818			X	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	<i>Harmothoe sp. 1</i>	Kinberg 1856		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	<i>Harmothoe sp. 2</i>	(Claparède 1870)		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	<i>Malmgrenia lunulata</i>	(Delle Chiaje 1830)	X		X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Sigalionidae	Sigalionidae sp. 1	Kinberg 1856		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Pionosyllis sp. indet.</i>	Malmgren 1867	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	Syllidae sp.	Grube 1850				X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	Syllidae sp. indet.	Grube 1850	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Acromegalomma vesiculosum</i>	(Montagu 1813)		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Euchone rosea</i>	Langerhans 1884				X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Pseudopotamilla reniformis</i>	(Bruguière 1789)	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Sabella spallanzanii</i>	(Gmelin 1791)				X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	Sabellidae sp.	Latreille 1825	X				X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Hydroides dianthus</i>	(Verrill 1873)		X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Hydroides norvegica</i>	Gunnerus 1768			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Serpula vermicularis</i>	Linnaeus 1767	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	Serpulidae sp. indet.	Rafinesque 1815	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	Spirorbinae sp.	Chamberlin 1919					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Vermiliopsis infundibulum</i>	(Philippi 1844)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Poecilochaetidae	<i>Poecilochaetus serpens</i>	Allen 1904			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Aonides oxicephala</i>	(Sars 1862)				X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Polydora ciliata</i>	(Johnston 1838)	X		X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Polydora sp.</i>	Bosc 1802		X			X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Prionospio sp. 1</i>	Malmgren 1867	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Prionospio sp. indet.</i>	Malmgren 1867	X		X		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Pseudopolydora antennata</i>	(Claparède 1869)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	Spionidae sp.	Grube 1850	X		X	X	

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	TAXON	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	Spionidae sp. indet.	Grube 1850					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sternaspida	Sternaspidae	<i>Sternaspis scutata</i>	(Ranzani 1817)			X	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	<i>Melinna palmata</i>	Grube 1870	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Pectinariidae	<i>Amphictene sp.</i>	Savigny 1822			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Pectinariidae	<i>Lagis koreni</i>	Malmgren 1866	X			X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Sabellariidae	<i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i>	(Leuckart 1849)			X	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Amphitrite cirrata</i>	Müller 1776			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Amphitrite sp. 1</i>	Müller 1771		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Eupolymnia nebulosa</i>	(Montagu 1819)	X		X	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Streblosoma bairdi</i>	(Malmgren 1866)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	Terebellidae sp.	Johnston 1846			X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Thelepus setosus</i>	(Quatrefages 1866)		X	X	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca diadema</i>	(Costa 1853)	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca sarsi</i>	Chevreaux 1888	X	X	X	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca sp. indet.</i>	Krøyer 1842	X		X	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca typica</i>	(Spence Bate 1856)			X	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Aoridae	<i>Microdeutopus anomalus</i>	(Rathke 1843)					X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Aoridae	<i>Microdeutopus sp.</i>	Costa 1853			X		
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Aoridae	<i>Microdeutopus sp. indet.</i>	Costa 1853	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Caprellidae	<i>Caprella scaura</i>	Templeton 1836		X	X	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Caprellidae	<i>Pseudolirius kroyeri</i>	(Haller 1879)	X			X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Corophiidae	<i>Apocorophium acutum</i>	(Chevreaux 1908)	X		X	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Dexaminidae	<i>Dexamine spinosa</i>	(Montagu 1813)	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Gammaridae	<i>Gammarus aequicauda</i>	(Martyinov 1931)				X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Isaeidae	<i>Microprotopus maculatus</i>	Norman 1867	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ischyroceridae	<i>Erichthonius brasiliensis</i>	(Dana 1853)		X	X		
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ischyroceridae	<i>Erichthonius punctatus</i>	(Dana 1853)				X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Leucothoidae	<i>Leucothoe oboa</i>	Karaman 1971	X	X	X		
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Lysianassidae	<i>Lepidepecreum longicorne</i>	(Spence Bate & Westwood 1861)	X			X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Melitidae	<i>Elasmopus rapax</i>	A. Costa 1853		X	X		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Oedicerotidae	<i>Deflexilodes subnudus</i>	(Norman 1889)					X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Oedicerotidae	<i>Periculodes longimanus</i>	(Spence Bate & Westwood 1868)	X	X	X		

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	TAXON	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Oedicerotidae	<i>Synchelidium haplocheles</i>	(Grube 1864)	X		X	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Pariambidae	<i>Pariambus typicus</i>	(Krøyer 1845)	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Phtisicidae	<i>Phtisica marina</i>	Slobber 1769	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Bodotriidae	<i>Bodotria scorpioides</i>	(Montagu 1804)		X			
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Bodotriidae	<i>Iphinoe serrata</i>	Norman 1867	X	X	X	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea		Cumacea sp. indet.	Krøyer 1846	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Diogenidae	<i>Diogenes pugilator</i>	(Roux 1829)				X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Hippolytidae	<i>Hippolyte</i> sp. indet.	Leach 1814					X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Panopeidae	<i>Dyspanopeus sayi</i>	(S. I. Smith 1869)	X		X	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Portunidae	<i>Carcinus aestuarii</i>	Nardo 1847			X	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Processidae	<i>Processa edulis</i>	(Risso 1816)		X			
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda		Brachyura sp. 1 megalopa	Latreille 1802		X			
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Anthuridae	<i>Cyathura carinata</i>	(Krøyer 1847)	X	X	X	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Arcturidae	Arcturidae sp.	Dana 1849	X	X			
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Idoteidae	<i>Idotea</i> sp.	Fabricius 1798	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Idoteidae	Idoteidae sp. indet.	Samouelle 1819	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Janiridae	Janiridae sp.	G. O. Sars 1897			X		
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Janiridae	Janiridae sp. indet.	G. O. Sars 1897				X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Munnidae	Munnidae sp. indet.	G. O. Sars 1897	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Sphaeromatidae	<i>Paracerceis sculpta</i>	(Holmes 1904)			X		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Tanaidacea	Tanaididae	Tanaididae sp.	Nobili 1906	X	X		X	
Arthropoda	Ostracoda			Ostracoda sp.	Latreille 1802			X		
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Bugulidae	<i>Bugula</i> sp.	Oken 1815					X
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Candidae	<i>Tricellaria inopinata</i>	d'Hondt & Occhipinti Ambrogi 1985			X	X	X
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Cryptosulidae	<i>Cryptosula pallasiana</i>	(Moll 1803)					X
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Schizoporellidae	<i>Schizoporella errata</i>	(Waters 1878)	X				
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Ctenostomatida	Vesiculariidae	<i>Amathia</i> sp.	Lamouroux 1812					X
Bryozoa	Stenolaemata	Cyclostomatida	Crisiidae	<i>Crisia</i> sp.	Lamouroux 1812					X
Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Didemnidae	<i>Didemnum</i> sp.	Savigny 1816				X	
Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Pyuridae	<i>Microcosmus</i> sp.	Heller 1877			X		
Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria		<i>Actiniaria</i> sp.	Hertwig 1882					X
Echinodermata	Asterozoa	Valvatida	Asterinidae	<i>Asterina gibbosa</i>	(Pennant 1777)	X				
Echinodermata	Holothurozoa	Dendrochirotrida	Cucumariidae	<i>Paraleptopentacta elongata</i>	(Düben & Koren 1846)			X	X	X
Echinodermata	Ophiurozoa	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	<i>Amphipholis squamata</i>	(Delle Chiaje 1828)			X	X	

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	TAXON	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Echinodermat a	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	<i>Amphiura chiojei</i>	Forbes 1843		X	X	X	
Echinodermat a	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	<i>Amphiura filiformis</i>	(O. F. Müller 1776)	X				
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcoidea	Arcidae	<i>Anadara transversa</i>	(Soy 1822)			X	X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Myoidea	Corbulidae	<i>Lentidium mediterraneum</i>	(O. G. Costa 1830)		X			
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Myoidea	Corbulidae	<i>Varicorbula gibba</i>	(Olivi 1792)	X	X	X		X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Arcuatula senhousia</i>	(Benson 1842)	X	X	X	X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Modiolus adriaticus</i>	Lamarck 1819	X				
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Modiolus barbatus</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)	X				
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Musculus subpictus</i>	(Cantraine 1835)					X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Mytilaster lineatus</i>	(Gmelin 1791)					X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Mytilaster minimus</i>	(Poli 1795)		X			
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	Lamarck 1819	X			X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Nuculoidea	Nuculidae	<i>Nucula nitidosa</i>	Winckworth 1930			X		
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pterioidea	Anomiidae	<i>Anomia ephippium</i>	Linnaeus 1758	X				
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pterioidea	Anomiidae	<i>Pododesmus patelliformis</i>	(Linnaeus 1761)		X			
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroidea	Leptonidae	<i>Hemilepton nitidum</i>	(W. Turton 1822)	X				
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroidea	Lucinidae	<i>Loripes orbiculatus</i>	Poli 1795	X	X		X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroidea	Lucinidae	<i>Loripinus fragilis</i>	(R. A. Philippi 1836)		X	X		
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroidea	Semelidae	<i>Abra nitida</i>	(O. F. Müller 1776)	X	X	X	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroidea	Tellinidae	<i>Macomangulus tenuis</i>	(da Costa 1778)		X			
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroidea	Tellinidae	<i>Moerella distorta</i>	(Poli 1791)				X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroidea	Veneridae	<i>Pitar rudis</i>	(Poli 1795)		X	X	X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroidea	Veneridae	<i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i>	(A. Adams & Reeve 1850)		X	X	X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroidea	Veneridae	<i>Timoclea ovata</i>	(Pennant 1777)	X	X			
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neotaenioglossa	Cerithiidae	<i>Bittium reticulatum</i>	(da Costa 1778)					X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neotaenioglossa	Hydrobiidae	<i>Hydrobia acuta</i>	(Draparnaud 1805)	X				
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neotaenioglossa	Rissoidea	<i>Pusillina sarsii</i>	(Lovén 1846)	X				
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Ptenoglossa	Muricidae	<i>Hexaplex trunculus</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)			X	X	X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Ptenoglossa	Nassariidae	<i>Tritia neritea</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)	X				X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Ptenoglossa	Nassariidae	<i>Tritia nitida</i>	(Jeffreys 1867)	X	X	X	X	X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Ptenoglossa	Nassariidae	<i>Tritia varicosa</i>	(W. Turton 1825)	X		X		X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Vetigastropoda	Trochidae	<i>Steromphala albida</i>	(Gmelin 1791)	X				

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	TAXON	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Vetigastropoda	Turbinidae	<i>Tricalia pullus</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)	X				
Porifera	Calcarea	Leucosolenida	Sycettidae	<i>Sycon raphanus</i>	Schmidt 1862				X	
Porifera	Demospongiae	Halichondrida	Halichondriidae	Halichondriidae sp.	Gray 1867					X
Porifera	Demospongiae	Haplosclerida	Chalinidae	<i>Halictona sp.</i>	Grant 1841					X
Porifera				Porifera sp. indet.	Grant 1836			X		

Table 2 – List of taxa identified at the coastal site.

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	SPECIES	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	<i>Capitella capitata</i>	(Fabricius 1780)					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	Capitellidae sp. indet.	Grube 1862		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	<i>Heteromastus filiformis</i>	(Claparède 1864)		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	<i>Notomastus sp. 1</i>	M. Sars 1851	X	X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	<i>Notomastus sp. indet.</i>	M. Sars 1851	X		X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	<i>Pseudoleiocarditella fauveli</i>	Harmelin 1964	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Maldanidae	<i>Chirimia biceps biceps</i>	(Sars 1861)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Maldanidae	<i>Euclymene lombricoides</i>	(Quatrefages 1866)	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Maldanidae	<i>Euclymene oerstedii</i>	(Claparède 1863)	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Maldanidae	<i>Leiochone leiopygos</i>	(Grube 1860)				X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Maldanidae	<i>Maldane glebifex</i>	Grube 1860	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Maldanidae	Maldanidae sp.	Malmgren 1867					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Maldanidae	<i>Praxillella gracilis</i>	(M. Sars 1861)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Chaetopterida	Chaetopteridae	Chaetopteridae sp.	Audouin & Milne Edwards 1833	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Aphelochoeta multibranchis</i>	(Grube 1863)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Aphelochoeta sp.</i>	Blake 1991	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Chaetozone zetlandica</i>	Mc Intosh 1911	X		X		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	Cirratulidae sp.	Ryckholt 1851					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Cirriformia tentaculata</i>	(Montagu 1808)			X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Dodecaceria concharum</i>	Ørsted 1843				X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Kirkegaardia dorsobranchialis</i>	(Kirkegaard 1959)				X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Tharyx sp. 1</i>	Webster & Benedict 1887		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Eunice sp. indet.</i>	Cuvier 1817					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Eunice vittata</i>	(Delle Chiaje 1828)	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Lysidice unicornis</i>	(Grube 1840)					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Marphysa sp. 1</i>	Quatrefages 1866		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Paucibranchia fallax</i>	(Marion & Bobretzky 1875)					
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Lumbrineridae	<i>Abyssoninoe hibernica</i>	(Mc Intosh 1903)	X				X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Lumbrineridae	<i>Hilbigneris gracilis</i>	(Ehlers 1868)	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Lumbrineridae	<i>Lumbrineris coccinea</i>	(Renier 1804)					

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	SPECIES	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Lumbrineridae	<i>Scoletoma fragilis</i>	(O. F. Müller 1776)	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Lumbrineridae	<i>Scoletoma laurentiana</i>	(Grube 1863)		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Oeonidae	<i>Arabella iricolor</i>	(Montagu 1804)	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Onuphidae	<i>Aponuphis bilineata</i>	(Baird 1870)	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Onuphidae	<i>Diopatra neapolitana</i>	Delle Chiaje 1841	X	X	X		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Onuphidae	<i>Onuphis sp.</i>	Audouin & Milne Edwards 1833					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Flabelligerida	Flabelligeridae	<i>Diplocirrus glaucus</i>	(Malmgren 1867)	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Flabelligerida	Flabelligeridae	<i>Pherusa plumosa</i>	(Müller 1776)					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Flabelligerida	Flabelligeridae	<i>Piromis eruca</i>	(Claparède 1869)					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Flabelligerida	Flabelligeridae	<i>Stylarioides sp.</i>	Delle Chiaje 1841	X	X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Flabelligerida	Flabelligeridae	<i>Trophoniella indica</i>	(Fauvel 1928)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Magelonida	Magelonidae	<i>Magelona alleni</i>	Wilson 1958				X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Magelonida	Magelonidae	<i>Magelona filiformis</i>	Wilson 1959	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Orbiniida	Orbiniidae	<i>Phylo foetida</i>	(Claparède 1869)	X		X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Orbiniida	Paraonidae	<i>Aricidea (Acmira) sp. 1</i>	Hartley 1981	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Orbiniida	Paraonidae	<i>Aricidea (Aedicira) sp. 1</i>	Hartman 1957	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Orbiniida	Paraonidae	<i>Levinsenia gracilis</i>	(Tauber 1879)		X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Orbiniida	Paraonidae	<i>Paradoneis lyra</i>	(Southern 1914)		X	X	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Oweniida	Oweniidae	<i>Galathowenia oculata</i>	(Zachs 1923)					
Annelida	Polychaeta	Oweniida	Oweniidae	<i>Owenia fusiformis</i>	Delle Chiaje 1844		X	X		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Aphroditidae	<i>Laetmonice hystrix</i>	(Savigny in Lamarck 1818)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Glyceridae	<i>Glycera tridactyla</i>	Schmarda 1861	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Hesionidae	<i>Hesionidae sp.</i>	Grube 1850					
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nephtyidae	<i>Nephtys hombergii</i>	Savigny in Lamarck 1818	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nereididae	<i>Nereididae sp.</i>	Blainville 1818		X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Phyllodocidae	<i>Mysta picta</i>	(Quatrefages 1866)	X	X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Phyllodocidae	<i>Phyllococe lineata</i>	(Claparède 1870)	X		X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Pilargidae	<i>Ancistrosyllis groenlandica</i>	Mc Intosh 1878	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Pilargidae	<i>Pilargis verrucosa</i>	Saint-Joseph 1899	X		X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Pilargidae	<i>Sigambra tentaculata</i>	(Treadwell 1941)	X	X	X		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	<i>Harmathoe antilopes</i>	Mc Intosh 1876			X		

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	SPECIES	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	<i>Harmothoe sp.</i>	Kinberg 1856		X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	<i>Malmgrenia lunulata</i>	(Delle Chiaje 1830)	X	X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	<i>Polynoinae sp. indet.</i>	Kinberg 1856	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Sigalionidae	<i>Sthenelais boa</i>	(Johnston 1833)			X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Chone sp.</i>	Krøyer 1856	X	X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Euchone rosea</i>	Langerhans 1884				X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Serpula concharum</i>	Langerhans 1880					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	Serpulidae sp.	Rafinesque 1815					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Spirobranchus triqueter</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)				X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Poecilochaetidae	<i>Poecilochaetus serpens</i>	Allen 1904		X	X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Polydora ciliata</i>	(Johnston 1838)		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Polydora sp.</i>	Bosc 1802					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Scolelepis (Scolelepis) sp. 1</i>	Blainville 1828		X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	Spionidae sp. indet.	Grube 1850	X		X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Spiophanes bombyx</i>	(Claparède 1870)		X	X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sternaspida	Sternaspidae	<i>Sternaspis scutata</i>	(Ranzani 1817)	X		X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	<i>Amage adpersa</i>	(Grube 1863)	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	<i>Ampharete acutifrons</i>	(Grube 1860)	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	<i>Ampharete octocirrata</i>	(Sars 1835)	X				
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	Ampharetidae sp.	(Malmgren 1866)				X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	Ampharetidae sp. indet.	(Malmgren 1866)	X				X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	<i>Amphicteis gunneri</i>	(M. Sars 1835)	X	X			
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	<i>Amphicteis midas</i>	(Gosse 1855)	X		X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	<i>Anobothrus gracilis</i>	(Malmgren 1866)			X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	<i>Melinna palmata</i>	Grube 1870		X			X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Pectinariidae	<i>Amphictene auricoma</i>	(O. F. Müller 1776)	X		X	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Pectinariidae	<i>Lagis koreni</i>	(Malmgren 1866)	X		X		
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Pectinariidae	<i>Pectinaria belgica</i>	(Pallas 1766)				X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Sabellariidae	<i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i>	(Leuckart 1849)		X	X	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Eupolymnia nebulosa</i>	(Montagu 1819)	X		X		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Streblosoma bairdi</i>	(Malmgren 1866)					

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	SPECIES	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	Terebellidae sp.	Johnston 1846					X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Trichobranchiidae	<i>Terebellides stroemii</i>	Sars 1835	X	X			
Annelida		Sipuncula	Phascolionidae	<i>Phascolion (Phascolion) strombus strombus</i>	(Montagu 1804)	X	X	X	X	X
Annelida		Sipuncula	Phascolosomatidae	<i>Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) granulatum</i>	Leuckart 1828					X
Annelida		Sipuncula	Sipunculidae	<i>Sipunculus (Sipunculus) nudus</i>	Linnaeus 1766	X	X	X		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca diadema</i>	(Costa 1853)	X		X		
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca sarsi</i>	Chevreux 1888	X	X	X	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca sp. indet.</i>	Krøyer 1842	X		X		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca spinipes</i>	Boeck 1861	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca typica</i>	(Spence Bate 1856)	X	X	X	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Aoridae	<i>Leptocheirus guttatus</i>	(Grube 1864)	X				X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Aoridae	<i>Microdeutopus sp. indet.</i>	Costa 1853	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Caprellidae	<i>Caprella equilibra</i>	Say 1818			X		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Caprellidae	<i>Caprella sp.</i>	Lamarck 1801	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Caprellidae	<i>Pseudolirius kroyeri</i>	(Haller 1879)					X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Corophiidae	Corophiidae sp. indet.	Leach 1814	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Corophiidae	<i>Medicorophium annulatum</i>	(Chevreux 1908)	X		X		
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Isaeidae	<i>Photis longicaudata</i>	(Spence Bate & Westwood 1862)					X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ischyroceridae	<i>Jassa marmorata</i>	Holmes 1905				X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Leucothoidae	<i>Leucothoe oboa</i>	Karaman 1971	X	X			X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Lysianassidae	<i>Lepidepecreum longicorne</i>	(Bate & Westwood 1861)		X	X		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Lysianassidae	<i>Orchomene humilis</i>	(Costa 1853)	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Melitidae	<i>Elasmopus rapax</i>	A. Costa 1853					X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Oedicerotidae	<i>Deflexilodes subnudus</i>	(Norman 1889)	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Oedicerotidae	<i>Westwoodilla rectirostris</i>	(Della Valle 1893)					
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Phoxocephalidae	<i>Harpinia dellavallei</i>	Chevreux 1910	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Stenothoidae	<i>Stenothoe monoculoides</i>	(Montagu 1813)	X				X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Bodotriidae	<i>Iphinoe serrata</i>	Norman 1867	X	X	X	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Diastylidae	<i>Diastylis rugosa</i>	Sars 1865	X		X	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Nannastocidae	<i>Campylaspis sp.</i>	G. O. Sars 1865	X				

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	SPECIES	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Crangonidae	<i>Crangon crangon</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)	X	X	X		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Ctenochelidae	<i>Gouretia denticulata</i>	(Lutze 1937)	X		X		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Diogenidae	<i>Clibanarius erythropus</i>	(Latreille 1818)		X			
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Diogenidae	<i>Diogenes pugilator</i>	(Roux 1829)					X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Ethusidae	<i>Ethusa mascarone</i>	(Herbst 1785)		X			
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Hippolytidae	<i>Eualus cranchii</i>	(Leach 1817)		X			X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Leucosiidae	<i>Illia nucleus</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)		X			
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Penaeidae	<i>Penaeus kerathurus</i>	(Forskål 1775)			X		
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Porcellanidae	<i>Pisidia sp. indet.</i>	Leach 1821		X	X		
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Portunidae	<i>Liocarcinus sp. indet.</i>	Stimpson 1871		X			
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Portunidae	<i>Polybius maculatus</i>	(Risso 1827)				X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Processidae	<i>Processa edulis</i>	(Risso 1816)	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Processidae	<i>Processa macrophthalma</i>	Nouvel & Holthuis 1957				X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Upogebiidae	<i>Upogebia tipica</i>	(Nardo 1869)		X			
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda		<i>Caridea sp. indet.</i>	Dana 1852		X			
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda		<i>Paguridea sp. indet.</i>	Latreille 1802		X			
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Bopyriidae	<i>Bopyriidae sp.</i>	Rafinesque 1815				X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Cirolanidae	<i>Cirolana sp.</i>	Leach 1818	X	X	X		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Gnathiidae	<i>Gnathia sp.</i>	Leach 1814	X		X		
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Leptostraca	Nebaliidae	<i>Nebalia sp.</i>	Leach 1814	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Tanaidacea	Apeudidae	<i>Apeudopsis latreillei</i>	(Milne-Edwards 1828)					X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Tanaidacea	Leptocheliidae	<i>Chondrochelia savignyi</i>	(Kroyer 1842)	X				
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Tanaidacea	Tanaididae	Tanaididae sp.	Nobili 1906			X		
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Tanaidacea		Tanaidacea sp. indet.	Dana 1849	X				
Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Phoxichilidiidae	<i>Anoplodactylus sp.</i>	Wilson 1878	X		X		X
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Ctenostomatida	Buskiidae	<i>Buskia socialis</i>	Hincks 1887				X	
Echinodermata	Asterozoa	Paxillosida	Astropectinidae	<i>Astropecten irregularis pentacanthus</i>	(Delle Chiaje 1827)	X	X	X	X	X
Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Spatangoida	Loveniidae	<i>Echinocardium cordatum</i>	(Pennant 1777)			X		X
Echinodermata	Holothurozoa	Apodida	Synaptidae	<i>Ostergrenia digitata</i>	Montagu 1815			X		X
Echinodermata	Holothurozoa	Dendrochirotda	Cucumariidae	<i>Paraleptopentacta elongata</i>	(Düben & Koren 1846)	X	X	X	X	X
Echinodermata	Holothurozoa	Dendrochirotda	Cucumariidae	<i>Paraleptopentacta tergestina</i>	(Sars 1859)	X				

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	SPECIES	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Echinodermat a	Holothuroidea	Dendrochiroti da	Cucumariidae	<i>Thyone fusus</i>	(O. F. Müller 1776)	X	X			X
Echinodermat a	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	<i>Amphipholis squamata</i>	(Delle Chiaje 1828)	X	X	X	X	X
Echinodermat a	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	<i>Amphiura chiajei</i>	Forbes 1843	X	X	X	X	X
Echinodermat a	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	<i>Amphiura filiformis</i>	(O. F. Müller 1776)	X	X	X	X	
Echinodermat a	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Ophiothricidae	<i>Ophiothrix fragilis</i>	(Abildgaard in O. F. Müller 1789)		X		X	
Echinodermat a	Ophiuroidea	Ophiurida	Ophiuridae	<i>Ophiura ophiura</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)	X				
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcoida	Arcidae	<i>Anadara transversa</i>	(Say 1822)	X		X		X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Myoida	Corbulidae	<i>Varicorbula gibba</i>	(Olivi 1792)	X	X	X		X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Myoida	Hiatellidae	<i>Hiatella arctica</i>	(Linnaeus 1767)			X	X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloida	Mytilidae	<i>Modiolus barbatus</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)	X			X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloida	Mytilidae	<i>Musculus subpictus</i>	(Cantraine 1835)					X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Nuculoida	Nuculanida	<i>Lembulus pella</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)		X	X	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Nuculoida	Nuculidae	<i>Nucula nitidosa</i>	Winckworth 1930	X	X	X	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pholadomyoid a	Thraciidae	<i>Thracia phaseolina</i>	(Lamarck 1818)		X	X		X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pterioida	Anomiidae	<i>Anomia ephippium</i>	Linnaeus 1758				X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pterioida	Limidae	<i>Limidae sp. indet.</i>	Rafinesque 1815			X		
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pterioida	Pectinidae	<i>Aequipecten opercularis</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)					X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroida	Cardiidae	<i>Acanthocardia tuberculata</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)			X		X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroida	Lucinidae	<i>Loripes orbiculatus</i>	Poli 1795		X			
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroida	Lucinidae	<i>Loripinus fragilis</i>	(R. A. Philippi 1836)			X	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroida	Lucinidae	<i>Lucinella divaricata</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)					X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroida	Pharidae	<i>Phaxas pellucidus</i>	(Pennant 1777)			X	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroida	Semelidae	<i>Abra alba</i>	(W. Wood 1802)		X	X	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroida	Semelidae	<i>Abra nitida</i>	(O. F. Müller 1776)		X	X	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroida	Solecturidae	<i>Azorinus chamasolen</i>	(da Costa 1778)		X	X	X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroida	Tellinidae	<i>Macomangulus tenuis</i>	(da Costa 1778)	X			X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroida	Tellinidae	<i>Moerella distorta</i>	(Poli 1791)	X	X	X	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroida	Veneridae	<i>Chamelea gallina</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)				X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Veneroida	Veneridae	<i>Pitar rudis</i>	(Poli 1795)	X	X	X	X	X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Cephalaspide a	Cylichnidae	<i>Cylichna cylindracea</i>	(Pennant 1777)			X		X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Cephalaspide a	Haminoeidae	<i>Haminoea navicula</i>	(da Costa 1778)			X		

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	SPECIES	AUTHOR	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Cephalaspidea	Philinidae	<i>Philine aperta</i>	(Linnaeus 1767)					X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Heterostropha	Turbonillidae	<i>Turbonilla pusilla</i>	(R. A. Philippi 1844)			X		
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neotaenioglossa	Calyptraeidae	<i>Calyptraea chinensis</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)		X	X		X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neotaenioglossa	Iravadiidae	<i>Hyala vitrea</i>	(Montagu 1803)			X	X	X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neotaenioglossa	Naticidae	<i>Euspira nitida</i>	(Donovan 1803)	X	X	X	X	X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neotaenioglossa	Turritellidae	<i>Turritellina tricarinata</i>	(Brocchi 1814)					X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Ptenoglossa	Conidae	<i>Bela sp.</i>	Leach 1847			X		X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Ptenoglossa	Eulimidae	<i>Eulima globra</i>	(da Costa 1778)	X	X	X	X	
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Ptenoglossa	Eulimidae	<i>Melanella polita</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)			X		
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Ptenoglossa	Muricidae	<i>Bolinus brandaris</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)	X			X	
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Ptenoglossa	Muricidae	<i>Hexaplex trunculus</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)			X		X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Ptenoglossa	Nassariidae	<i>Tritia varicosa</i>	(W. Turton 1825)		X	X		X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Pulmonata	Ellobiidae	Ellobiidae sp.	L. Pfeiffer 1854 (1822)			X		X
Mollusca	Scaphopoda	Dentaliida	Dentaliidae	<i>Antalis inaequicostata</i>	(Doutzenberg 1891)	X	X	X	X	X
Nemertea	Anopla		Cerebratulidae	<i>Cerebratulus marginatus</i>	Renier 1804				X	
Platyhelminthes		Polycladida		Polycladida sp. indet.	Lang 1884				X	

Table 3 – List of fouling taxa colonizing marine litter items on the lagoon (LV) and coastal (CS) sites.

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	SPECIES	AUTHOR	LV	CS
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	<i>Capitella minima</i>	Langerhans, 1880		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Capitellida	Capitellidae	Capitellidae sp.	Grube, 1862		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Coulleriella bioculata</i>	(Keferstein, 1862)		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Chaetozone gibber</i>	Woodham & Chambers 1994	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	Cirratulidae sp.	Ryckholt, 1851		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Cirriiformia tentaculata</i>	(Montagu 1808)	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Cirratulida	Cirratulidae	<i>Dodecaceria concharum</i>	Ørsted 1843	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Eunice vittata</i>	(Delle Chiaje 1828)	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Lysidice ninetta</i>	Audouin & H Milne Edwards, 1833		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Lysidice unicornis</i>	(Grube 1840)	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Marphysa sanguinea</i>	(Montagu 1813)	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Lumbrineridae	<i>Abyssoninoe hibernica</i>	(Mc Intosh, 1903)		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Lumbrineridae	<i>Hilbigneris gracilis</i>	(Ehlers, 1868)		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Aphroditidae	Aphroditidae sp.	Malmgren 1867	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nereididae	<i>Composetia hircinicola</i>	(Eisig 1869)	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nereididae	<i>Neanthes acuminata</i>	(Ehlers 1868)	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nereididae	Nereididae sp.	Blainville, 1818		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nereididae	<i>Perinereis cultrifera</i>	(Grube, 1840)		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	<i>Harmothoe fraserthomsoni</i>	McIntosh 1897	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	<i>Harmothoe sp.</i>	Kinberg, 1856		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Salvatoria limbata</i>	(Claparède 1868)	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	Syllidae sp.	Grube 1850	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Syllis gracilis</i>	Grube, 1840		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Syllis nigricirris</i>	Grube, 1863		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Amphiglena mediterranea</i>	(Leydig 1851)	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Sabella pavanina</i>	Savigny 1822	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Sabella sp.</i>	Grube, 1870		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Hydroides dianthus</i>	(Verrill 1873)	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Hydroides norvegica</i>	Gunnerus, 1768		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Serpula concharum</i>	Langerhans, 1880		X

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	SPECIES	AUTHOR	LV	CS
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	Serpulidae sp.	Rafinesque 1815	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Spirobranchus triqueter</i>	(Linnaeus, 1758)		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Spiroboris</i> sp.	Daudin 1800	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Vermiliopsis infundibulum</i>	(Philippi 1844)	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Polydora</i> sp.	Bosc, 1802		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	<i>Ampharete octocirrata</i>	(Sars, 1835)		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	Ampharetidae sp.	Malmgren 1866	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Sabellariidae	<i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i>	(Leuckart 1849)	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Amphitritides</i> sp.	Augener 1922	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Eupolymnia nebulosa</i>	(Montagu 1819)	X	X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Neoamphitrite edwardsii</i>	(Quatrefages, 1866)		X
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	Terebellidae sp.	Johnston 1846	X	
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Thelepus setosus</i>	(Quatrefages 1866)	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca typica</i>	(Spence Bate 1856)	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Aoridae	<i>Microdeutopus</i> sp. indet.	Costa 1853	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Caprellidae	<i>Caprella equilibra</i>	Soy 1818	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Caprellidae	<i>Caprella scaura</i>	Templeton 1836	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Corophiidae	<i>Apocorophium acutum</i>	(Chevreux 1908)	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Corophiidae	Corophiidae sp. indet.	Leach 1814	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Dexaminidae	<i>Dexamine spinosa</i>	(Montagu 1813)	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ischyroceridae	<i>Erichthonius brasiliensis</i>	(Dana 1853)	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ischyroceridae	<i>Erichthonius punctatus</i>	(Spence Bate, 1857)		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ischyroceridae	<i>Jassa marmorata</i>	Holmes, 1905		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Leucothoidae	<i>Leucothoe spinicarpa</i>	(Abildgaard 1789)	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Lysianassidae	<i>Lysianassa castae</i>	H. Milne Edwards 1830	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Melitidae	<i>Elasmopus rapax</i>	Costa 1853	X	X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Stenothoidae	<i>Stenothoe monoculoides</i>	(Montagu, 1813)		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Stenothoidae	<i>Stenothoe valida</i>	Dana, 1852		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Hippolytidae	<i>Hippolyte leptocerus</i>	(Heller 1863)	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Panopeidae	<i>Dyspanopeus sayi</i>	(Smith 1869)	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pilumnidae	<i>Pilumnus hirtellus</i>	(Linnaeus, 1761)		X
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Porcellanidae	<i>Pisidia</i> sp.	Leach, 1821		X

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	SPECIES	AUTHOR	LV	CS
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Anthuridae	<i>Anthura gracilis</i>	(Montagu 1808)	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Anthuridae	<i>Cyathura carinata</i>	(Krøyer 1847)	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Arcturidae	Arcturidae sp.	Dana 1849	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Janiridae	Janiridae sp.	G. O. Sars 1897	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Munnidae	Munnidae sp.	G. O. Sars 1897	X	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Sphaeromatidae	<i>Paracerceis sculpta</i>	(Holmes 1904)	X	
Arthropoda	Thecostraca	Thoracica	Balanidae	<i>Amphibalanus amphitrite</i>	(Darwin, 1854)		X
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Bugulidae	<i>Bugula neritina</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)	X	
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Bugulidae	<i>Bugula sp.</i>	Oken, 1815		X
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Candidae	<i>Tricellaria inopinata</i>	d'Hondt & Occhipinti Ambroggi 1985	X	
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Schizoporellidae	<i>Schizoporella sp.</i>	Hincks 1877	X	X
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Ctenostomatida	Buskiidae	<i>Buskia socialis</i>	Hincks 1887	X	X
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Ctenostomatida	Vesiculariidae	<i>Amathia sp. 1</i>	Lamouroux 1812	X	
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Ctenostomatida	Vesiculariidae	<i>Amathia sp. 2</i>	Lamouroux 1812	X	
Bryozoa	Stenolaemata	Cyclostomatida	Crisiidae	<i>Crisia sp.</i>	Lamouroux 1812	X	
Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Clavelinidae	<i>Clavelina sp.</i>	Savigny 1816	X	
Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Didemnidae	Didemnidae sp.	Giard 1872	X	
Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Didemnidae	<i>Didemnum sp.</i>	Savigny 1816	X	
Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Pyuridae	<i>Microcosmus sp.</i>	Heller 1877	X	
Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Pyuridae	<i>Pyura sp.</i>	Molina 1782	X	
Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Styelidae	Styelidae sp.	Herdman 1881	X	
Cnidaria	Anthozoa	Actinaria	Aiptasiidae	<i>Exaiptasia diaphana</i>	(Rapp, 1829)		X
Cnidaria	Anthozoa	Actinaria	Sagartiidae	<i>Cereus pedunculatus</i>	(Pennant, 1777)		X
Cnidaria	Anthozoa	Zoanthidea	Epizoanthidae	<i>Epizoanthus arenaceus</i>	(Delle Chiaje, 1841)		X
Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Asterinidae	<i>Asterina gibbosa</i>	(Pennant 1777)	X	
Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	<i>Amphipholis squamata</i>	(Delle Chiaje, 1828)		X
Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	<i>Amphiura chiajei</i>	Forbes 1843	X	
Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Ophiothricidae	<i>Ophiothrix fragilis</i>	(Abildgaard in OF. Müller 1789)	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcoida	Arcidae	<i>Anadara transversa</i>	(Say 1822)	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Myoida	Gastrochaenidae	<i>Rocellaria dubia</i>	(Pennant 1777)	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Myoida	Hiatellidae	<i>Hiatella arctica</i>	(Linnaeus, 1767)		X

PHYLUM	CLASSIS	ORDO	FAMILIA	SPECIES	AUTHOR	LV	CS
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Arcuatula senhousia</i>	(W. H. Benson 1842)	X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Gregariella petagnae</i>	(Scacchi, 1832)		X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Modiolus barbatus</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Musculus subpictus</i>	(Cantraine, 1835)		X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Mytilaster lineatus</i>	(Gmelin 1791)	X	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytiloidea	Mytilidae	<i>Mytilaster minimus</i>	(Poli, 1795)		X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Ostreoidea	Ostreidae	<i>Ostrea edulis</i>	Linnaeus 1758	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pterioidea	Anomiidae	<i>Anomia ephippium</i>	Linnaeus 1758	X	X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pterioidea	Anomiidae	<i>Pododesmus squama</i>	(Gmelin, 1791)		X
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pterioidea	Pectinidae	<i>Aequipecten opercularis</i>	(Linnaeus, 1758)		X
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Notaspidea	Pleurobranchidae	Pleurobranchidae sp.	Gray 1827	X	
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Ptenoglossa	Muricidae	<i>Hexaplex trunculus</i>	(Linnaeus 1758)	X	
Porifera	Calcarea	Leucosolenida	Syconidae	<i>Sycon sp.</i>	Risso 1827	X	
Porifera	Demospongiae	Halichondrida	Halichondriidae	Halichondriidae sp.	Gray, 1867		X
Porifera	Demospongiae	Halichondrida	Halichondriidae	Halichondriidae sp. 1	Gray 1867	X	
Porifera	Demospongiae	Halichondrida	Halichondriidae	Halichondriidae sp. 2	Gray 1867	X	